

An Insight into the Replication Mechanism of Smallpox and Monkeypox Viruses

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Abstract

Poxviruses are a family of large, enveloped DNA viruses that infect large numbers of vertebrates and invertebrates, causing severe disease. Some prominent members of the family, viz. variola virus (causative agent of smallpox), and monkeypox (mpox) virus (causes human mpox) are of great concern globally. The crucial enzyme, viz. the DNA polymerase (pol) involved in the multiplication of these viruses in human cells, is studied and found that it shows striking similarities to most of the DNA pols already reported from prokaryotes and eukaryotes and their pol domain uses the same catalytic amino acids in their active sites as reported for other DNA pols. For example, the smallpox and mpox viral catalytic amino acids in their pol catalytic core regions are the same, viz. -MQ⁴YTYK¹IIANSVY⁸GLM- and -MQ⁴YTYK¹IVANSVY⁸GLM-, respectively and are also the same as that of the host enzymes, viz. the human replicative δ and ϵ DNA pols, viz. -RQ⁴LALK¹VSANSVY⁸GFT- and -LQ⁴LAHK¹CILNSFY⁸GYV-, respectively. Furthermore, the poxviral proofreading (PR) exonuclease domain is made up of the same active site amino acids as in other DNA/RNA pols, including the host replicative DNA pols, and belongs to DEDD(Y) superfamily of PR exonucleases. In spite of their active site similarities, the smallpox and mpox viral replicative DNA pols showed only 23.75 and 23.69 per cent identities, respectively, to the human replicative δ pol. In contrast, the regulatory zinc-binding motifs (ZBMs) which are typically found in human and other eukaryotic replicative pols (α , δ , ϵ) at their C-terminal domains (CTDs) are absent in these poxviral DNA pols, but a HNH type homing endonuclease motif, which is identified in the poxviral pols, is absent in humans and other eukaryotic replicative pols. Presently approved vaccines and antivirals for smallpox and mpox are also discussed.

Keywords: Smallpox; Monkeypox; Variola virus; Vaccinia virus; Mpox virus; DNA polymerase; Polymerase active site; Proofreading exonuclease active site; Cidofovir; Brincidofovir; Ribavirin

1. Introduction

Depending on the nature of their genetic material, viruses are broadly classified into RNA or DNA viruses. In spite of the major difference in their genetic material, both equally cause serious human diseases, including pandemic ones. For example, some of the pandemic ones, like human immunodeficiency viruses (HIVs), human influenza viruses, human respiratory syncytial viruses, SARS-CoVs, etc., are caused by RNA viruses whereas some of the other serious human diseases, like Hepatitis B (Herpadnaviruses), Herpes simplex virus, Chickenpox (Herpesvirus), Smallpox and Monkeypox (Poxviruses), Respiratory diseases (Adenoviruses), Cervical cancer (Papillomaviruses), etc., are caused by DNA viruses. Based on the structure of their genome and replication strategies, the RNA and DNA viruses are further classified into three main groups: i) double-stranded (ds) RNA (dsRNA) viruses, ii) positive-sense single-stranded RNA (+ssRNA) viruses, and iii) negative-sense single-stranded RNA (-ssRNA) viruses and i) ds DNA viruses (e.g., Poxviruses, Herpesviruses), ii) ss DNA viruses (e.g., Parvoviruses, Adeno-associated viruses), and iii) circular-dsDNA viruses, (Pararetroviruses, e.g., Cauliflower mosaic virus of plants, Herpadnaviruses of vertebrates). As both RNA and DNA viruses cause serious human diseases, it is imperative to understand the fundamental aspects of their lifecycles and replication mechanisms to develop cost-effective vaccines and antiviral drugs to contain the spread of these viruses.

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Among the DNA viruses, the poxviruses are the largest of all known animal viruses (sizes ranging from 220–450 nm long, 140–260 nm wide and 140–260 nm thick) and are also the deadliest ones. They infect most of the vertebrates and invertebrates, causing a variety of diseases of veterinary and medical importance [1]. They are enveloped viruses and possess ds DNA genomes and are mostly oval or brick-shaped. Their genomes comprise of a single, linear molecule of ds DNA of 128–375 kbp with ~200 distinct genes. It is interesting to note that their ds DNA genomes do not have free ends, but are covalently-closed with hairpin-like structures at their ends. These hairpin termini are AT-rich, incompletely base-paired and exist in inverted and complementary forms.

The poxviruses belong to the family of Poxviridae. The poxviridae family is further classified into two subfamilies, viz. Chordopoxvirinae, which infect vertebrates, and Entomopoxvirinae, which infect insects. The subfamilies are further classified into different genera. For example, there are 18 recognized genera in the Chordopoxvirinae subfamily and 4 in the Entomopoxvirinae subfamily (Table 1). Chordopoxviruses have a restricted and specific host array and only 4 of them are known to infect humans also. It should be noted that the poxviruses are resistant to ambient temperatures and may survive many years in dried scabs. Some of the poxviruses have a limited host range, but others are capable of infecting a wide range of related animals as well. Therefore, these viruses are generally placed into specific groups, largely based on the type of animal(s) they infect. It is interesting to note that humans are the sole hosts for two of the poxviruses, viz. variola (smallpox) and molluscum contagiosum.

Table 1 Classification of Poxviruses

Family: Poxviridae	
Subfamily 1: Chordopoxvirinae (from the Phylum Chordata; Vertebrate hosts)	
1. Genus: <i>Avipoxvirus</i> (Bird)#	10. Genus: <i>Oryzopoxvirus</i> (Rodents)
2. Genus: <i>Capripoxvirus</i> (Goat)	11. Genus: <i>Orthopoxvirus</i> * (Gk = straight)
3. Genus: <i>Centapoxvirus</i> (From central Africa, e.g., yokapox virus)	12. Genus: <i>Parapoxvirus</i> * (Gk = beside or next to)
4. Genus: <i>Cervidpoxvirus</i> (Deer)	13. Genus: <i>Pteropoxvirus</i> (wing footed)
5. Genus: <i>Crocodylidpoxvirus</i> (Crocodile)	14. Genus: <i>Salmonpoxvirus</i> (Salmon)
6. Genus: <i>Leporipoxvirus</i> (Hare)	15. Genus: <i>Sciuripoxvirus</i> (Squirrel)
7. Genus: <i>Macropoxvirus</i> (Large footed)	16. Genus: <i>Suipoxvirus</i> (Swine)
8. Genus: <i>Molluscipoxvirus</i> * (Clam, Snail)	17. Genus: <i>Vespertilionpoxvirus</i> (Bat)
9. Genus: <i>Mustelpoxvirus</i> (Weasel)	18. Genus: <i>Yatapoxvirus</i> * (Yaba monkey)
Subfamily 2: Entomopoxvirinae (Gk. Entomon = Insect, Insect hosts)	
1. Genus: <i>Alphaentomopoxvirus</i>	
2. Genus: <i>Betaentomopoxvirus</i>	
3. Genus: <i>Deltaentomopoxvirus</i>	
4. Genus: <i>Gammaentomopoxvirus</i>	

Adapted from McInnes *et al.* [2]

#The genus *Avipoxvirus*, under natural conditions, infects and causes diseases in avians only; e. g., fowlpox, pigeonpox, and turkeypox viruses are closely related and are not strictly host-specific.

*Those which infect humans are found only among four genera of the Chordopoxvirinae subfamily, viz. *Orthopoxvirus*, *Parapoxvirus*, *Molluscipoxvirus* and *Yatapoxvirus* (highlighted in red).

Molluscum contagiosum virus is the only member of the genus *Molluscipoxvirus* and humans are the natural reservoirs for the virus. The human infections are restricted to the skin and affect primarily children and immuno-compromised adults. The unique feature of the virus is; it is restricted to human keratinocytes which build the outer layer of the skin.

Members of the genus, *Yatapoxvirus* (Yata is derived from the two recognized members of the class, viz. the **yaba** monkey tumour virus and **tanapox** virus, which infect primates in equatorial Africa. Infections can spread to humans by insect vectors

The yaba monkey tumor virus and yaba-like disease virus, like all members of the genus *Yatapoxvirus*, are considered as potential human pathogens.

The orthopox- and parapoxviruses of the Chordopoxvirinae subfamily are further classified into Zoonotic and Non-zoonotic types, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Classification of Orthopox- and Parapoxviruses

Genus: Orthopoxvirus	
<u>Zoonotic types</u>	<u>Non-zoonotic types</u>
1. Monkeypox virus	1. Variola virus
2. Vaccinia virus	2. Volepox virus
3. Buffalopox virus	3. Ectromelia virus
4. Camelpox virus	4. Raccoonpox virus
5. Cowpox virus	5. Skunkpox virus
6. Elephantpox virus	6. Uasin Gishu disease virus
	7. Taterapox virus
Genus: Parapoxvirus	
<u>Zoonotic types</u>	<u>Non-zoonotic types</u>
1. Bovine papular stomatitis virus	1. Auzduk disease virus
2. Orf virus (Sheep)	2. Parapoxvirus of red deer
3. Pseudocowpox virus (milker's nodules)	3. Chamois contagious ecthyma virus
4. Sealpox virus	

1.1. Smallpox Virus (Variola Virus)

Among the poxviral diseases, the smallpox is the most severe one and also highly contagious. It easily spreads from person to person by contact. It is caused by the smallpox virus which is generally known as variola virus (VARV, variola is the Latin name for smallpox). It is a member of the Poxviridae family and Chordopoxvirinae subfamily and belongs to the genus Orthopoxvirus. [The term "smallpox" is used to distinguish it from the "greatpox" (syphilis)]. It is interesting to note that the smallpox disease has been one of the deadliest diseases in human history and it killed about millions of people in the 20th century alone. However, in the 1980s, after an intensive immunization program with a vaccine prepared from the vaccinia virus (VACV), the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the disease eradicated. On 26 October 1979, WHO announced the eradication of smallpox, and it was officially declared on 8 May 1980, during its 33rd assembly. (VACV is closely related to VARV, but relatively nonpathogenic and therefore, used in the preparation of smallpox virus vaccines. It is also widely used as a model for poxviruses in the laboratory to understand the biochemistry and molecular biology of the VARV, in general). As the routine vaccination for smallpox ended worldwide in the 1970s, most of today's population lacks immunity against the virus and hence, the smallpox attack could be especially harmful and deadly. It is also suggested that the ending of the vaccination programme for smallpox, accidentally created an opening for the emerging human mpox attacks in recent times. And thus, in the absence of the smallpox vaccine, the mpox virus has certainly proven its ability to evolve freely and spread widely, leading to today's international emergency situation [3].

Poxviruses have developed a distinct replication strategy in human cells, i.e., unlike other DNA viruses, they replicate in the cytoplasm itself. The genomes of ~30 poxviruses have been completely sequenced, including several strains of variola and vaccinia viruses. At least two major variants of the VARVs are reported, and they cause two different forms of the smallpox disease, viz. i) Variola major: it is a more severe one with case-fatality rates of 30%–40%, and ii) Variola minor: it is less severe with a much-reduced case-fatality rates of 1% or less. Outbreaks of the Variola major were the only known type until the end of the 19th century. Most of those who survived the Variola major had distinctive residual facial pockmarks, and some were blind. However, at the genome level, the two variants are very similar. For example, they differ only in about <2% of the roughly 1,85,000 unique DNA nucleotides and almost all of the encoded proteins are essentially identical in both [4].

1.2. Mpox Virus

1.2.1. Infection and Diagnosis

Mpox virus disease has now become an emerging poxviral disease and is spread worldwide by the mpox virus. It was first discovered in Denmark (1958) in monkeys kept for research. However, the first reported human case of mpox virus disease was a nine-month-old boy in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) in 1970. Initially, the mpox virus was found mainly in the tropical rainforests in Central, East and West Africa, where small mammals such as squirrels, Gambian pouched rats, dormice, and various species of monkeys acted as carriers of the mpox virus.

The mpox virus is also a brick- or oval-shaped virus like the smallpox virus, ranging in size from 200-250 nm in diameter. It belongs to the Poxviridae family along with the other poxviruses, like variola, vaccinia, camelpox and cowpox viruses; all of which are pathogenic to humans [5]. A recent WHO report shows that the human mpox cases are escalating

worldwide and have emerged as a significant threat to the global population. In 2022, human mpox virus has spread worldwide, causing 99,581 mpox cases in 121 countries [6]. Therefore, in August 2024, the WHO declared it as a '*public health emergency of international concern*' for the first time in May 2022 and the second time in August 2024. Therefore, for this epidemic to be controlled, the epidemiology, its lifecycle, multiplication mechanism in human cells and genetics must be better understood. Interestingly, as its genome and lifecycle are very closely related to vaccinia and variola viruses, their vaccines and antiviral drugs maybe of some use to control the spread of the virus. Furthermore, as the mpox virus is a close relative of the smallpox virus and also due to its antigenic similarity to the smallpox virus, smallpox vaccines cross-protect against mpox viral infections too.

Even though originally it was a zoonotic virus, now it has been found that it is capable of human-to-human transmission too and spreads through close contact. Transmission occurs through exposure to bodily fluids, lesions on the skin or on internal mucosal surfaces such as in the mouth or throat, respiratory particles and contaminated objects. Its clinical presentation is similar to smallpox, i.e., like 10-14 days of incubation followed by formation of skin rashes. The rashes are painful with enlarged lymph nodes with headache, muscle ache, back pain, sore throat and fever that can progress to severe complications, including pneumonia and encephalitis. Hence, the differentiation of these diseases by clinical presentation alone is quite challenging.

Identification of mpox virus infections in humans is becoming more difficult because of other viral and bacterial infections, with similar conditions. Therefore, it is important to distinguish mpox virus infections from other viral infections, like chickenpox, measles, scabies, herpes, syphilis and other sexually transmitted infections, bacterial skin infections for specific mpox treatments. Testing of blood for mpox virus is not recommended as the viremic phase may have already passed at the time of the onset of rash. Furthermore, antibody detection methods may not be useful as they do not distinguish between different Orthopoxviruses. Therefore, the preferred laboratory test for mpox virus is the detection of the mpox viral DNA by polymerase chain reaction (PCR) techniques like the real-time PCR (RT-PCR). Now, the RT-PCR has become the gold standard for diagnosing the human mpox virus. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has granted Emergency Use Authorization (EUA) to seven diagnostic tests based on RT-PCR [7 and references therein].

1.2.2. Classification of Mpox Virus

The mpox viral strains are classified into two main clades: the more pathogenic Congo Basin (Central Africa) clade (also known as Clade I) and the West African clade (also known as Clade II). Clade I infections are known to be associated with greater disease severity and more pronounced as compared to clade II infections. Furthermore, a recent data has shown that the clade I is capable of increased human-to-human transmission compared to clade II. The Clades I and II are further classified into 2 subclades as Ia and Ib and IIa and IIb. www.who.int/news/item/12-08-2022-monkeypox-experts-give-virus-variants-new-names. The Ib and IIb are evolved variants of I and II, respectively, with the potential for human-to-human transmission. Thus, there are 4 known circulating variants of the virus, as clades Ia, Ib, IIa and IIb [8].

The Clade Ia strain of the virus was the first one to be discovered to infect humans in 1970 from Central Africa. It infected mostly children, and was known to be mainly transmitted animal to human (a zoonotic type).

The Clade Ib strain of the virus was also discovered in Central Africa and is distinguished by its capability of human-to-human transmissions, including through sexual contact. Therefore, this led to a surge of human mpox cases in the late 2023. However, as of August 2024, clade Ib has also been detected beyond Africa. For example, now the Clade Ib has been detected in the United Kingdom, Sweden, Thailand, India, Germany and six other African countries that had never reported mpox infections before. Among the nations, the DRC has been hit particularly hard by the clade Ib. In fact, the country has reported nearly 36,000 suspected infections and more than 1,000 deaths from mpox in 2024.

The Clade IIa strain of the virus is the least-studied one. It has been mainly reported in Guinea, Liberia and Côte d'Ivoire. Its modes of transmissions are not fully understood, but it is likely that it spreads through close contact, and there is no documented evidence of sexual transmission.

The Clade IIb strain of the virus is known to spread from human-to-human, including through sexual contact. It is responsible for the 2022-2023 global outbreaks that has infected more than 90,000 people and continues to infect more people till this day [8].

1.3. Genomes of Smallpox and Mpox Viruses: Salient Features

All poxviruses possess very similar genomic structures, i.e., they all have a linear, ds DNA genome that varies from 130 to 230 kbp. Their genomic DNA contains an identical, but oppositely oriented sequences called inverted terminal repeats (ITRs) at their ends [9, 10]. The ITRs include a set of short tandem repeats and terminal hairpins [11]. The terminal hairpin-like structures connect the linear ds DNA strands into closed termini [12, 13]. It is suggested that these closed termini could protect the genomes from host nucleases and ensure genome's integrity. The terminal hairpin-like structures contain predominantly AT residues and is incompletely base-paired. A central region of the genome is highly conserved among different Orthopoxviruses and the late genes are clustered near the central region. The ends of the genome are hypervariable and may contain extensive deletions and symmetrical sequence rearrangements [14]. It is interesting to note that much of the poxvirus genome encodes gene products that serve to evade the host immune responses.

Different strains of the smallpox viral genomes are completely sequenced. The smallpox viral variant that causes smallpox, *Variola major* (with an overall fatality rate of ~30%), has a genome that consists of a single, linear, ds DNA molecule that is 1,86,102 bp long with a coding capacity for ~187 proteins (~150 of which are very similar (with >90% identity) between smallpox and vaccinia viruses). It possesses relatively small (725 bp) ITRs containing three 69-bp direct repeat elements. It has a 105-base telomeric end-loop that is maximally base-paired with 17 mismatches [15]. The other smallpox viral variant, viz. *Variola minor*, causes mild smallpox (with an overall fatality rate of ~1% or less) and its genome varies slightly from the *Variola major*. It contains a linear ds DNA genome of 1,86,986 bp with ~206 potential ORFs. The smallpox virus genome is contained within a biconcave core, with two lateral bodies on either side [16].

The most studied among the poxviral genomes is the vaccinia viral genome. It is similar to the smallpox virus genome and consists of 1,91,636 bp with a base composition of 66.6% A + T with 198 "major" protein-coding regions and 65 overlapping "minor" regions, for a total of 263 potential genes. Interestingly, it is used in the preparation of smallpox vaccines as it is similar to smallpox, but is less harmful [17]. As in other poxviral genomes, in the vaccinia viral genome also, the two strands of viral DNA molecule are cross-linked at both termini with hairpin-loops and the hairpin termini are AT-rich and exist in inverted-complementary forms and incompletely base-paired. In the case of vaccinia virus, the hairpins are 104 nucleotides in length and contain a 4-nucleotide loop. The hairpin is at the end of long-ITRs containing sets of short, tandemly repeated sequences [18]. Unlike variola virus, in the vaccinia viral genome the long-inverted terminal repeats (LTR) are of about 10 kbp and are found at the distal ends of the genome. The LTRs are further characterized by the presence of direct tandem repeats of a 70-bp sequences, arranged in two blocks of 13 and 17 copies, respectively.

The mpox viral genomic structure also closely resembles that of other Orthopoxviruses. The mpox virus possesses a 1,97,201 bp ds DNA with a G+C content of 33.01%. The virus contains about 190 nonoverlapping open reading frames (ORFs), four of which are located in the ITR sequence. Both terminal regions are variable which include a 6379 bp ITRs with approximately 80 bp long hairpin loop, 70 or 54 bp short, tandem repeats and unique ITR sequences and the coding region [19 and references therein, [20]. Its genome is characterized by a highly conserved central core region, with variable regions at the left and right ends, and tandemly repeated ITRs on both the ends. The central core region of mpox virus shares more than 90% sequence homology with other Orthopoxviruses. The central conserved region encodes "housekeeping" genes involved in transcription, replication and virion assembly. The genes in the terminal regions encode proteins involved in host range and pathogenesis [21]. It is interesting to note that the mpox and smallpox viral genomes are genetically highly similar with a 96.3% identity between them [22].

1.4. Lifecycle of Poxviruses

Poxviruses, like the variola virus that causes smallpox, are transmitted primarily through direct contact with infected persons or through respiratory droplets from an infected person's coughs and sneezes. There are at least five major structural elements that make up the infectious virion: i) Central core, ii) Core wall, iii) Lateral bodies (function(s) not known), iv) Inner membrane, and v) Outer membrane envelope carrying the surface proteins. The central core essentially consists of the viral genome and the viral enzymes essential for early genes transcription.

The lifecycle of poxvirus is unique from other DNA viruses in that they do not enter the nucleus of the infected cells and the whole lifecycle is completed within the host cell cytoplasm itself. After infection, they have an incubation period of 7–17 days. During that time, a massive viral replication takes place in lymphatic tissues resulting in the swelling of lymph nodes. Then it returns to body surfaces (to mucosa and skin with multiple lesions) paving the way for subsequent infections. The lifecycle essentially involves 7 stages: i) Attachment, entry and early genes transcription, ii) Uncoating,

iii) Late genes transcription and replication, iv) Viral assembly, vi) Envelopment of the viral particles by intracellular membranes and maturation of viral particles, and vii) Release of mature virions.

In the first step, the virus binds to its specific receptor on the host cells, viz. the glycosaminoglycans present on the host cell surface act as the receptor for poxvirus attachment (Glycosaminoglycans are anionic polysaccharides and consist of repeating disaccharide units of uronic acid and hexosamine. They include hyaluronan, chondroitin sulphate, dermatan sulphate, heparan sulphate, heparin and keratan sulphate). Senkevich *et al.* [23] found that the entry of the virus was through the membrane fusion and is highly conserved among the poxvirus family, implying that this primary mechanism, developed in their early evolution, remains unchanged.

Expression of the early genes starts in the next step. Viral genes are expressed in two phases: early and late. The early genes encode non-structural proteins, while the late genes encode structural proteins needed for the final assembly of the progeny virions. As mentioned earlier, the viral core contains not only the viral genome, but also the full transcriptional machinery needed to initiate early gene expression *in situ*, including enzymes such as the viral DNA-dependent RNA polymerase (DdRp), capping enzyme, poly(A) polymerase, topoisomerase, and transcription factors. This is evident from the fact that the synthesis of the viral early gene mRNAs starts within minutes after viral entry. The early gene transcripts are extruded through the pores of the viral core and are translated in the host cell cytoplasm. The early genes are ~100 in number which constitute nearly half of the viral genome, encode the proteins needed for uncoating, transcription factors (needed for the subsequent late gene expression), and the full repertoire of enzymes and proteins needed for the replication of the viral genome. After early gene expression, the viral core undergoes a complex process of uncoating in which the wall of the viral core dissolves and the genome is released. Transcription of late genes and DNA replication occurs following release of the genome from the core.

In the final step of the lifecycle, the viral particles are assembled and get enveloped by the intracellular membrane and released. The viral genome, together with viral enzymes and factors required for transcription of the early subset of genes, is packaged in the core of infectious virus particles. Interestingly, the DNA replication proteins, in contrast to those involved in early gene transcription, are not packaged in the virions, but are transcribed and translated from viral mRNAs later. In the early stages of the viral assembly, two distinct infectious viral particles are present: intracellular mature virions (IMVs) and extracellular enveloped virions (EEVs). The IMVs possess a single membrane structure whereas the EEVs possess a double-membrane structure. In addition to the above, these two different viral particles vary in the composition of their envelope membranes and surface glycoproteins. The IMVs are the most abundant viral particles due to the absence of an additional lipid membrane, which gives them a simpler and more robust structure. They are released upon cell lysis and enter new host cells through direct fusion and endocytosis which may be important for their animal-to-animal transmission mode while EEVs move to the peripheral region and are released via membrane fusion [24-26]. It is interesting to note that the EEVs are antigenically distinct from IMVs. Therefore, targeting any stage of the virus lifecycle holds promise for the development of effective antiviral interventions against poxviruses.

1.5. Poxviral Replication Machinery

1.5.1. Vaccinia virus Replication Machinery

Genomic DNA replication is the crucial step in the lifecycle of poxviruses. As the vaccinia virus is safer, it is used as a model system to study the biochemistry, genetics and molecular biology of poxviruses, in general. Therefore, a great deal of information is available on its replication machinery. As mentioned elsewhere, unlike other DNA viruses, poxviruses replicate in the cytoplasm and their genomic DNAs encode all the enzymes and proteins that are necessary for their DNA replication. The replication starts with an initiation site on the genomic DNA. Specific replication initiation site is proposed to be possibly within the conserved sequence between the hairpin loop and the direct repeats. Furthermore, it is also proposed that the poxvirus replication is by a primer-dependent mechanism and that too by self-priming. In the self-priming model, a nick in one strand of the poxvirus genome creates a 3'-OH end, which is used as the growing end for the addition of dNTPs that are complementary to the template DNA and further elongated. The presence of the HNH endonuclease motif identified in the poxviral DNA pol may play a role in the initiation step. The elongated strands then fold back, but the replication complex continues to add dNTPs, resulting in the formation of concatemers where multiple copies of the same DNA genome are linked in series. Thus, the viral genomic DNA is proposed to be replicated by a rolling circle mechanism (i.e., where the replication initiator protein nicks a parental strand to create a primer end with 3'-OH for leading-strand synthesis) as long, unbranched, head-to-tail concatemers. The concatamers are further processed by a viral endonuclease, i.e., by the Holliday junction resolvase to produce unit genomes.

For the replication and processing of the genomic DNA of vaccinia virus, at least six virus-encoded enzymes and proteins are required. These include a helicase-primase (encoded by the viral gene, *D5*), a ss DNA-binding protein (encoded by

the viral gene, *I3*), a protein kinase (encoded by the viral gene, *B1*), a 117-kDa DNA polymerase (encoded by the viral gene, *E9*), a processivity factor (encoded by the viral gene, *A20*) and an uracil DNA glycosylase (encoded by the viral gene, *E4*). The A20 processivity factor is a non-enzymatic bridging protein that bridges E9 (DNA pol) and D4 protein uracil DNA glycosylase (UDG). (UDG is ubiquitous in biological systems and it functions as DNA repair enzyme by initiating the base-excision-repair pathway, BER). The integration of a UDG in the DNA pol holoenzyme is a unique feature of the poxvirus replication machinery, which might functionally couple the processes of DNA repair to DNA synthesis (Fig. 1A). The B1 kinase phosphorylates a cellular DNA-binding protein called BAF (Barrier to Autointegration Factor) and prevents the latter from blocking the vaccinia viral replication. In addition to the above enzymes, a viral flip endonuclease (FEN1) (encoded by the viral gene, *G5*) participates in ds DNA break repair, a Holliday junction resolvase (encoded by the viral gene, *A22*) resolves the concatemers and a DNA ligase (encoded by the viral gene, *A50*) joins the DNA ends to make an exact copy of the viral genome to be packaged into the viral particles.

1.5.2. Mpox virus Replication Machinery

Similar to the VACV, the mpox virus also replicates its genome in the cytoplasm. The mpox virus possesses a 1.97,201 bp ds DNA genome and encodes ~181 proteins, including all the enzymes and proteins that are required for its DNA replication. Interestingly, the DNA replication machinery is extremely conserved in Orthopoxviruses, and the sequence identity is more than 97% between VACV and mpox virus. Thus, the mpox virus replication machinery is structurally and functionally very similar to VACV. For example, the protein F8 is the DNA pol (E9 in vaccinia virus), A22 is the processivity factor (A20 in vaccinia virus) and E4 is the UDG (D4 in vaccinia virus). These three form the DNA replication machinery, where the U-shaped A22 subunit links F8 to E4 as discussed in vaccinia virus (Fig. 1A). In A22, the two terminal domains, the NTD and CTD, bring close the F8 and E4. A recent cryo-EM studies of the replication machinery of the mpox virus have revealed that in the replication complex, these three proteins, F8-A22-E4 form a novel circular structure [27]. The biochemical assays show that the replication complex with these three proteins is much more efficient in synthesizing DNA than F8 alone, which is consistent with the studies of the homologous VACV DNA pol complex in which the E9-A20-D4 heterotrimer complex synthesizes DNA more efficiently than E9 alone (Fig. 1B).

Figures 1A & 1B Schematic diagrammes showing similarity in the organization of the subunits of vaccinia and mpox virus DNA replication complexes

In vaccinia virus, the catalytic subunit of the DNA pol E9 binds to the essential processivity factor, A20 which is evident from the copurification of it along with DNA Pol E9 subunit. The E9-A20 heterodimer in turn binds to D4 to form the functional polymerase holoenzyme. (The numbers in brackets indicate approximate molecular masses of the subunits).

Similarly, in the mpox virus, the F8 is the catalytic subunit of the DNA pol; A22 is the processivity factor and E4 is the UDG. A22 links E4 to F8 to form the active heterotrimer. (The numbers in brackets indicate approximate molecular masses of the subunits). (During BER, the UDGs in both the pol complexes remove the uracil from DNA, which could arise through misincorporation of dUTP or spontaneous deamination of cytosine. Thus, the UDG initiates the BER pathway by hydrolyzing the glycosidic bond, linking uracil to a deoxyribose sugar, creating an apurinic (AP) site which is cleaved by an AP endonuclease in the subsequent step and repaired.

The main catalytic subunit of the DNA pol complex of vaccinia, variola and mpox viruses invariably follow the same domain organization as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 A schematic diagramme showing domain organization of the mpox viral DNA pol

1.6. Vaccines and Antiviral Drugs for the Treatment of Smallpox and Mpox Viruses

Both vaccines and antiviral drugs are available to treat the smallpox and mpox viral diseases. VACV vaccine protects people from smallpox by helping their bodies to develop immunity to smallpox. The smallpox vaccine is not actually made from the smallpox virus, but from VACV, which is also a poxvirus very similar to the smallpox virus, but less harmful. Interestingly, the smallpox vaccine contains live VACV produced from animals, i.e., it is not a killed or weakened like many other viral vaccines. (Other live viral vaccines currently in use are for measles, mumps, rubella, and chickenpox). The *second-generation vaccines* consist of again live VACV, but grown in the chorioallantoic membrane or cell culture techniques. By this way, it is produced in a sterile environment unlike the *first-generation vaccines* that contain the skin bacteria from the animal from where the VACV was grown on. The *third-generation vaccines* are based on attenuated VACV that are much less virulent and carry lesser side effects. The attenuated VACV maybe of a replicating or non-replicating type.

The Modified Vaccinia Ankara (MVA) virus, used in Bavarian Nordic's vaccine (MVA-BN), does not replicate in the body and hence, is much safer and the preferred vaccine for the current mpox outbreak. It is a replication-incompetent variant of the VACV that was developed in Germany through serial passage. The MVA-BN is manufactured by Bavarian Nordic (BN) by growing the MVA in cell culture. The MVA is now the only vaccine that the FDA has explicitly approved for human mpox treatment. Another vaccine recommended by the WHO is LC16m8. It is an attenuated, minimally replicating smallpox vaccine that is derived from the Lister strain of VACV. The WHO has granted 'Emergency use listing (EUL)' for the LC16m for mpox treatments, making it the second mpox vaccine to be recommended by WHO with EUL for the LC16m8 mpox vaccine.

Even though the use of MVA and other vaccines reduced the disease at-risk populations, but failed to deliver complete protection. Therefore, mRNA vaccines have been developed now. The mRNA-1769 vaccine is found to enhance viral control and disease attenuation compared to the MVA vaccine, highlighting the potential for mRNA vaccines to mitigate future pandemic poxviral threats [6]. It was found that among the emerging vaccine platforms, mRNA vaccines offer unprecedented flexibility, speed, and immunogenicity.

The poxvirus vaccines have their own drawbacks. Firstly, the poxvirus vaccines protect mpox, only to a limited extent. Secondly, the vaccine is very expensive (costs ~ \$100 per dose). There are not so many countries in Africa and in other third-world countries that can afford this vaccine at this cost. Furthermore, in addition to the cost, the smallpox vaccine was found to be far from ideal. For example, the smallpox vaccine maybe fatal to people with weakened immune systems, as it contains the live VACV and hence, is not suitable for those with weakened immune systems. Therefore, there is an urgent need for the development of cost-effective antiviral drugs for human mpox virus. So far, only a few antiviral compounds have been approved by regulatory authorities. Therefore, it is suggested that the initial efforts to identify inhibitors that should focus on enzymes which play an essential role in the poxvirus replication. Thus, it is important to analyze the active/binding sites of the crucial enzyme(s)/protein(s) in the lifecycle of the virus. And one of them is obviously the viral DNA pol. Therefore, understanding its replication and subsequent resistance mechanisms is fundamental for the development of novel and cost-effective antiviral drugs. Some of the antiviral drugs that are in use currently are discussed in the following section.

Current antiviral treatment options for mpox viral infection are limited to the use of a small number of antiviral drugs that are licensed for the human smallpox disease and is recommended by the CDC, 2024 (www.cdc.gov/poxvirus/mpox/clinicians/treatment.html). These include tecovirimat (commercially known as Tpoxx®) and brincidofovir (BCV, commercially known as Tembexa®), or its active compound cidofovir (CDV, (S)-1-(3-hydroxy-2-phosphonylmethoxypropyl) cytosine, commercially known as Vistide®). Tecovirimat is the first antiviral agent that was specifically indicated for the treatment of smallpox in adults and paediatric patients and was approved by the FDA (USA) in 2018 [29]. It is an inhibitor of the OPXV F13 envelope protein (also known as VP37), important for viral egress [30, 31].

The second line of antiviral drugs are the DNA pol inhibitors. Among the viral DNA pol inhibitors tested in the *in vitro* laboratory assays are CDV and BCV. They were found to be potent, broad-spectrum antiviral compounds that exhibit anti-poxvirus activities including mpox virus clades I, IIa, and IIb. (CDV is a prodrug, which requires two phosphorylation steps by the host cellular enzymes to be converted into its active form. For example, the phosphorylation by the host kinases, first convert the CDV to CDV-monophosphate (CDV-p) and then to CDV-diphosphate (CDV-pp). The CDV-pp is a competitive inhibitor of DNA pols with respect to dCTP, i.e., the CDV-pp acts as a dCTP analogue during the polymerization reactions. Maximum inhibition of enzyme activity occurs when two or more CDV-pp molecules are incorporated successively. If only one molecule of CDV-pp is incorporated, the replication continues, but at a decreased elongation rate. However, due to the presence of a 3'-OH group, the CDV does not act as a

chain terminator, in contrast to all the approved anti-HIV nucleoside inhibitors. Secondly, the CDV-pp could also act as a pyrophosphate (pp) analogue that binds to the pp-binding site on the DNA pol and could prevent the cleavage of the pp group from incoming dNTP, and thus, arresting the chain elongation [23, 32, 33].

Using CDV directly is found to be a problem, as it is a divalent anion exhibiting low bioavailability. Furthermore, in patients with impaired renal function or undergoing renal replacement therapy, its metabolites can accumulate in proximal renal tubular cells, leading to kidney damage. Therefore, in order to overcome these limitations on the use of CDV, its lipid conjugate, viz. the BCV (hexadecyloxypropyl-cidofovir) has been developed. The BCV shows improved bioavailability and significant safety profiles [34]. Furthermore, as it is not a substrate for anion transporters present in renal proximal tubules, its use substantially reduces the risk of drug-induced nephrotoxicity. Upon entry into infected cells, the BCV is converted to CDV and interferes with the DNA pol reactions as discussed above. It was approved by the FDA in 2021 for the treatment of smallpox [35]. Apart from BCV, other compounds based on structural modifications of the CDV have also been developed. For instance, NPP-669 is synthesized by linking a long-chain sulphonate to CDV. This modification improves its solubility in water and its affinity for lipid through the alkyl chain modification. This structural modification is found to enhance the metabolic stability and bioavailability while reducing nephrotoxicity as well [36].

Ribavirin, an inhibitor of RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) activity, has also been widely used against RNA and DNA viruses. It is a synthetic purine nucleoside derivative of guanosine. It inhibits guanosine triphosphate formation and thus, prevents capping of viral mRNAs and also blocks viral RdRp activity. Thus, it exhibits a broad-spectrum antiviral activity and inhibits both DNA and RNA viruses such as hepatitis C virus, human influenza viruses A and B, parainfluenza, human respiratory syncytial virus, paramyxovirus, HIV, variola (smallpox), mpox viruses, etc.

2. Material and Methods

The protein sequence data of poxviral DNA pols, eukaryotic replicative pols (α , ϵ and δ) from yeasts, plants and animals and DNA pols of bacteria and bacteriophages were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. Along with the conserved motifs identified by the bioinformatics analysis and from the data already available from biochemical, site-directed mutagenesis (SDM), cryogenic-Electron Microscopy (cryo-EM) and X-ray crystallographic analyses on these replicative pols, are used to identify the possible amino acids at the active sites of smallpox and mpox viral replicative pols.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. MSA Analysis of the replicative DNA Pol from Poxviruses

Figure 3 shows the MSA of the DNA pols from poxviruses belonging to different genera that infect both vertebrates and invertebrates (only the required regions for the discussions are shown). The variola, vaccinia and mpox viral DNA pol sequences are highlighted. The N-terminal region (NTD) (~160 amino acids) starts with a highly conserved decapeptide in all, in addition to a few invariant aromatic amino acids. This region is followed by a highly conserved PR exonuclease domain. The PR exonuclease domain contains the typical, completely conserved active site amino acids (highlighted in light blue) as found in other PR DNA pols. A ZBM connects the N-terminal and the PR exonuclease domains. Additionally, a consecutive Ns and a -KLDS- direct repeat are observed in the PR exonuclease domain (highlighted). The PR exonuclease domain is followed by the pol domain which is also highly conserved in all. Interestingly, the pol catalytic amino acids are completely conserved (highlighted in yellow) and in close agreement with other DNA pols reported from both pro- and eukaryotes. The two typical motifs, -SLYPS- and -YGD TDS- which are the characteristic of the B-family pols are found before and after the proposed pol active site, respectively (Table 3). However, a significant difference is observed in the last amino acid of the first pentapeptide motif in all poxviral pols where the usual S is replaced by an N (-SLYPN-) [37]. However, the second motif is completely conserved in all the poxviral DNA pols (highlighted) as reported in other B-family pols. Highly conserved Ds (highlighted in dark green) in the pol domain are implicated in the catalytic metal-binding.

Another marked difference observed between the human and poxviral replicative pols is the absence of the two regulatory ZBMs in their CTDs. For example, the catalytic subunits of all the three eukaryotic replicative DNA pols (pol α , ϵ and δ), contain two invariant ZBMs in their CTDs and they are named CysA and CysB. The CysA acts as the regular ZBM and binds a Zn^{2+} whereas the CysB binds a $-[4Fe-4S]-$ cluster [38]. Another significant difference is that the CTDs of the poxviral DNA pols contain a-HNH- type of endonuclease motif $^{-896}HH^1SNYKSADNPN^{11}MYLVTEYN^8-$ marked in bracket and also highlighted) (numbering with respect to mpox viral DNA pol).

The HNH endonuclease motif is a small nucleic acid-binding motif (~30 amino acids in length) found in all kingdoms of life and is particularly very common in the genomes of bacteria and their phages and also in organellar genomes. It contains the following three invariant amino acids, **-H-----N---H-** (where the last H is replaced by an N in some enzymes. However, the **-HNN-** motif functions in the same way as the **-HNH-** motif) (Fig. 4). The HNH endonucleases essentially involve in a metal ion-mediated cleavage of DNAs.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of the DNA polymerases from different poxviruses

tr A0A0M3ZCQ4 A0A0M3ZCQ4_9POXV	-----MDIRC	VNWFE	NKGD-IKYIYLKAITKSSTVIFIRFDYNYHYVYDTE---L	48	
tr A0A068EE70 A0A068EE70_9POXV	-----MDIRC	VNWFE	NKGE-IKYIYLKAINRESNVVIFIRFNYYHYVYDASKE---L	48	
tr A0A2H4X2A1 A0A2H4X2A1_9POXV	-----MDIRC	VNWFE	NKGE-IKYIYLKAINRESNVVIFIRFNYYHYVYDASKE---L	48	
tr A0A7G0XLV5 A0A7G0XLV5_FOWFV	-----MDIRC	VNWFE	NKGE-TKYIYLKAINRESNVIFIRFNYYHYVYDASKE---L	48	
sp P21402 DPOL_FOWFN	-----MDIRC	VNWFE	NKGE-TKYIYLKAINRESNVIFIRFNYYHYVYDASKE---L	48	
tr A0A2C9DSJ8 A0A2C9DSJ8_9POXV	-----MELRC	INWFE	NRGE-ERFLYLKAKTRHSESVFIRFRYYFYHVLNDNDVVGEGT	51	
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	-----MEIRC	LNWFE	ARGE-ERALYLKAKTRAGDTLDFVRFPHYYHYVVDGGTTLST-L	50	
tr Q8UZ49 Q8UZ49_9POXV	-----MEIRC	LNWFE	TRGE-ELALYLKTKTRAGDTLDFVRFPHYYHYVVDGGTTLST-L	50	
sp Q84173 DPOL_ORFN2	-----MELKC	LNWFE	NRGNSRFLFLKARRADNAVYVYLRVQHFYVVRADAVAD-I	51	
tr U3UBH8 U3UBH8_9POXV	MKIYSANK	MDVRC	VNWFE	SRGE-RKFLYLKARTREGAAVYFRFNRYFYVYVSEATLAS-L	58
tr A0A1U9H104 A0A1U9H104_9POXV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SRGE-TRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr A0A0K1LE69 A0A0K1LE69_9POXV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr A0A212PWR2 A0A212PWR2_COWFX	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SRGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr Q2QJ3 Q2QJ3_9POXV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr Q0GP22 Q0GP22_HSPV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr Q6R2N7 Q6R2N7_9POXV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr A0A2P1JPK6 A0A2P1JPK6_9POXV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SHGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr Q2QJ19 Q2QJ19_RACVI	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SRGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDDVYKS-L	50	
tr Q2QJ10 Q2QJ10_9POXV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SRGE-NRFLYLKSRSRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr Q2QJ11 Q2QJ11_9POXV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SRGE-NRFLYLKSRCRNGETVFIRFPHYFYVVTDEIYQS-L	50	
tr A0A223FMP5 A0A223FMP5_9POXV	-----MEVRC	INWFE	SRGE-ERFLYLKSRCKNNDTVFIRFPYYFYVVTDEVYKS-L	50	
tr G3EIC1 G3EIC1_9POXV	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SRGD-ERFLYLKARCKNGDTVFIRFPYYHYVVTDDIYHS-L	50	
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	-----MDVRC	INWFE	SKGD-NRYFLKARNKDLKTFPFRFPYYFYALYALYDEKYTS-L	50	
tr A0A7D0UGA2 A0A7D0UGA2_9POXV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SKGEDNRLFLKARTKESKTIFIRFKYYFYVVTEDVYNS-L	51	
tr G0T3C8 G0T3C8_9POXV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SKGD-TRLIFLKARTKESKTIFIRFSYYFYVVTDDVYK-L	50	
tr A0A1B2LFP1 A0A1B2LFP1_9POXV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SKGN-ERFLFLKARNRQSETIFLRFNFYFYVYAVTEDVYMS-L	50	
tr A0A5C0PQP2 A0A5C0PQP2_9POXV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SKGN-ERFLFLKARNRQSETIFLRFNFYFYVYAVTEDVYIS-L	50	
tr A0A1C9HHQ2 A0A1C9HHQ2_LSDV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SKGN-ERFLFLKARNRQSETIFLRFNFYFYVYAVTEDVYIS-L	50	
tr A0A2H4EUX3 A0A2H4EUX3_SHEV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SKGN-ERFLFLKARNRRSETIFLRFNFYFYVYAVTEDVYLS-L	50	
tr A0A2P1A9C0 A0A2P1A9C0_SHEV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SKGN-ERFLFLKARNRRSETIFLRFNFYFYVYAVTEDVYLS-L	50	
tr E2CZS9 E2CZS9_9POXV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SKGD-KRFLFLKARNKLETFVRFPHYFYVVTEDVYKT-L	50	
tr A0A881SY50 A0A881SY50_SWFV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SRGD-RRFLFLKARNRRSETIFIRFPYYFYVVTEDVYDT-L	50	
tr Q08FV4 Q08FV4_DPV83	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SRGE-KRFLFLKARNKLETFIRFPYYFYVVTDDVYKS-L	50	
tr A0A3S7SVZ5 A0A3S7SVZ5_9POXV	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SRGE-KRFLFLKARNKLETFIRFPYYFYVVTDDVYKS-L	50	
tr Q08FD4 Q08FD4_DPV84	-----MEIKC	INWFE	SRGE-KRFLFLKARNKLETFIRFPYYFYVVTDDVYKS-L	50	
			:::::**** :*: :*: :*: :*: :*: :*::		

tr A0A0M3ZCQ4 A0A0M3ZCQ4_9POXV	DFTPIDSSSELGQFNIIIDIEIVDKDIRDVDRKTYTKHLRLVKDNR-KNRQKGYLSEYLD	107
tr A0A068EE70 A0A068EE70_9POXV	EYKPKERLDLGRFKIINIDEKLNTRDIRYVEQRDYTTSELVLVKDLK-RNREKQYLQEQYLD	107
tr A0A2H4X2A1 A0A2H4X2A1_9POXV	EYKPKERLDLGRFKIINIDEKLNTRDIRYVEQRDYTTSELVLVKDLK-RNREKQYLQEQYLD	107
tr A0A7G0XLV5 A0A7G0XLV5_FOWPV	EYKPNCEIDLGRFKIINIDEKLNTRDIRYVEPRNYTTSELVLVKDLK-RNREKQYLQEQYLD	107
sp P21402 DPOL_FOWFN	EYKPNCEIDLGRFKIINIDEKLNTRDIRYVEPRNYTTSELVLVKDLK-RNREKQYLQEQYLD	107
tr A0A2C9DSJ8 A0A2C9DSJ8_9POXV	LFPQQELTHLGSFNIVFIDELVSIETIANLRRCFCVKDLYLTKDLARRKTRSRYLADFLN	111
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	APPPRAASALGEFELACIDETLARA-DALHAPTRFRSQWLWLEEAQPRQIAGALLAEFMH	109
tr Q8UZ49 Q8UZ49_9POXV	APPPRAASALGEFELACIDETLARA-DALHAPTRFRSQWLWLEEAQPRQIAGALLAEFMH	109
sp Q84173 DPOL_ORFN2	AQPLAWTRALGPMSSVVIDEIVARS-AKIPERQRSEIELCLVASERKLAPPEVFMSEFLN	110
tr U3UBH8 U3UBH8_9POXV	APPRAHAEPLGRMSIIDIEEVSRD-ANLRFRPRREEDLWLVAEPHRRSIVGAYMTDFLD	117
tr A0A1U9H104 A0A1U9H104_9POXV	APPPLNARPMGKMRIIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRNIIQNSAMDEFLN	109
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	APPPFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VAR67	APPPFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A0K1LE69 A0A0K1LE69_9POXV	APPPFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A212PWR2 A0A212PWR2_COWFX	APPPFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr Q2QJ3 Q2QJ3_9POXV	APPPFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	SPPFFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRSIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr Q0GP22 Q0GP22_HSPV	SPPFFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRSIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr Q6R2N7 Q6R2N7_9POXV	SPPFFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRSIQONATMDEFLN	109
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	SPPFFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRSIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A2P1JPK6 A0A2P1JPK6_9POXV	SPPFFNARPMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRSIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr Q2QJ19 Q2QJ19_RACVI	APPPLNARHMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIRDRKCSISDMWLEIEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr Q2QJ0 Q2QJ0_9POXV	APPPLNARHMGKMRITIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr Q2QJ1 Q2QJ1_9POXV	SPPPLNARNGMGMRTIDIDETISYIN-LDIKDRKCSVADMWLEIEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A223FMP5 A0A223FMP5_9POXV	SPPAFRAKPLGEMKTIIDIDETISYIN-IDINDRKSISVSEMWLEIEPKKRNISKVSMDDEFLN	109
tr G3EIC1 G3EIC1_9POXV	SPEAFRSKSLGEMKIINIEEIVSYS-IDIDDRNISINSMWLEIEPKKRNISKIYMDEFLN	109
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	TTPAFKSVFISGKMTIDISEYISYIN-VDSNETRKKVDVWILWLEPKKRSIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A7D0UGA2 A0A7D0UGA2_9POXV	LPRYSSEFLGSMIDIINSEYISINTVEDNITREKSNQNVWLIKDKKRNINVKIMNDEFLN	111
tr G0T3C8 G0T3C8_9POXV	IFPKYSSSELGSMNIIIDVSENINT-VVTNITKDEKHNWVWLIKEIKKRNVES-VMGDEFLN	108
tr A0A1B2LPK1 A0A1B2LPK1_9POXV	SPPAYSDPLGNMNLIDISERVSNNH-VTDVEKNTNVNWLKEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A5C0PQP2 A0A5C0PQP2_9POXV	SPPAYSDPLGNMNLIDISERVSNNH-VTEVEKNTNVNWLKEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A1C9HHQ2 A0A1C9HHQ2_LSDV	SPPAYSDPLGNMNLIDISERVSNNH-VTDVEKNTNVNWLKEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A2H4EUX3 A0A2H4EUX3_SHEV	SPPAYSDPLGNMNLIDISERVSNNH-VTDVEKNTNVNWLKEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A2P1A9C0 A0A2P1A9C0_SHEV	SPPAYSDPLGNMNLIDISERVSNNH-VTDVEKNTNVNWLKEPKKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr E2CZS9 E2CZS9_9POXV	VPIPTASIFLDSMIIIDISEYTSNY-VSDVTRKKTMANIWLKEKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr A0A881SY50 A0A881SY50_SWPV	SFSPYMSEFLGNMNIIDISEYTSNY-VTDIKRECTNVNWLKEKRNIIQONATMDEFLN	109
tr Q08FV4 Q08FV4_DPV83	KPSIYGSEFLGSMIDIIDISEYTSNY-VTDINRKRRTNVNWLKEIKKQISIKVIMDEFLN	109
tr A0A3S7SVZ5 A0A3S7SVZ5_9POXV	KPSIYGSEFLGSMIDIIDISEYTSNY-VTDIHRKRRTNVNWLKEIKKQISIKVIMDEFLN	109
tr Q08FD4 Q08FD4_DPV84	KPSIYGSEFLGSMIDIIDISEYTSNY-VTDIHRKRRTNVNWLKEIKKQISIKVIMDEFLN	109

tr A0A0M3ZCQ4 A0A0M3ZCQ4_9POXV	ITWFWLLNSIKPDGCYEINMEKLSAISRD	YHKEPNKLFTEIPLFD	IKYTYLCEFDIEC	167
tr A0A068EE70 A0A068EE70_9POXV	ISWFWLLNNITPDGCYKIDIEHLTLIKRD	YHCDDVSKVFIQEIPIFE	VKFTYLLFDIEC	167
tr A0A2H4X2A1 A0A2H4X2A1_9POXV	ITWFWLLNNITPDGCYKIDIEHLTPIKRD	YHCDDVSKVFIQEIPIFE	VKFTYLLFDIEC	167
tr A0A7G0XLV5 A0A7G0XLV5_FOWPV	ITWFWLLNNITPDGCYKIDIEHLTPIKRD	YHCDDVSKVFIQEIPIFE	VKFTYLLFDIEC	167
sp P21402 DPOL_FOWFN	ITWFWLLNNITPDGCYKIDIEHLTPIKRD	YHCDDVSKVFIQEIPIFE	VKFTYLLFDIEC	167
tr A0A2C9DSJ8 A0A2C9DSJ8_9POXV	ITWFWLLNIDIALDGCYRVDPCVPLGPGC	YHCHDDPKTAFAVAIPAFAE	VRYTYLFDIEC	171
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	ITWFWLLRNDIEPNGCYRVPDAELEPVCAR	YHCAAPRRAFATRVPLFE	VTHTYLFEDIEC	169
tr Q8UZ49 Q8UZ49_9POXV	ITWFWFLRNEIEPNGCYRVPDAELEPVCAR	YHCAAPRRAFATRVPLFE	VTHTYLFEDIEC	169
sp Q84173 DPOL_ORFN2	VSWFFVAHDIDPDGCYRVDPALELRDLGSS	YHCHDDPGACFAEKIIPRFN	VTRSYLFDIEC	170
tr U3UBH8 U3UBH8_9POXV	VTWFFIANEIDPDGCYAVDESLLEEVRAG	YHCHDDPKRCFAARIPRFD	VQRTYLFEDIEC	177
tr A0A1U9H104 A0A1U9H104_9POXV	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDDQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VAR67	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDDQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr A0A0K1LE69 A0A0K1LE69_9POXV	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr A0A212PWR2 A0A212PWR2_COWFX	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr Q2QJ3 Q2QJ3_9POXV	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr Q0GP22 Q0GP22_HSPV	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr Q6R2N7 Q6R2N7_9POXV	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr A0A2P1JPK6 A0A2P1JPK6_9POXV	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr Q2QJ19 Q2QJ19_RACVI	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRNCFAKEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr Q2QJ0 Q2QJ0_9POXV	ISWFWISNRISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRSCFAEKIIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr Q2QJ1 Q2QJ1_9POXV	ISWFWISNGISPDGCYSLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDPRSCFAEKIIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr A0A223FMP5 A0A223FMP5_9POXV	ITWFFIINISPDGCYMLDEQYLTKINNG	YHCHDDTQKCFANEIPRFD	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr G3EIC1 G3EIC1_9POXV	ITWFFIINEISPDGCYSLDDTYLTKINSS	YHCHDDIKRCFKIIRDFN	I PRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	ITWFWMLNVCVDPGCYVIDIKMLEKINDN	YHCHNDPQQLFLNIPRFD	VRSYLFEDIEC	169
tr A0A7D0UGA2 A0A7D0UGA2_9POXV	NNWFFISNNISPEGCYIIDIEKLEKINSQ	YHCHDDPKCEFSIKIDRFE	VNNSYLFEDIEC	171
tr G0T3C8 G0T3C8_9POXV	NNWFFITNNISPEGCYKIDIDSLEKINNSQ	YHCHDDPKSLFKFEPINRFD	VTISYLFEDIEC	168
tr A0A1B2LPK1 A0A1B2LPK1_9POXV	VSWFFISNNISPEGCYSINVEKLLKINEQ	YHCHDYPKECFATPINRFD	INRSYLFEDIEC	169
tr A0A5C0PQP2 A0A5C0PQP2_9POXV	ISWFFISNNISPEGCYSINVEKLLKINEQ	YHCHDYPKECFATPINRFD	INRSYLFEDIEC	169
tr A0A1C9HHQ2 A0A1C9HHQ2_LSDV	VSWFFISNNISPEGCYSINVEKLLKINEQ	YHCHDYPKECFATPINRFD	INRSYLFEDIEC	169
tr A0A2H4EUX3 A0A2H4EUX3_SHEV	VSWFFILNNSISPEGCYSINVEKLLKINEQ	YHCHDYPKECFATPINRFD	INRSYLFEDIEC	169
tr A0A2P1A9C0 A0A2P1A9C0_SHEV	VSWFFISNNISPEGCYSINVEKLLKINEQ	YHCHDYPKECFATPINRFD	INRSYLFEDIEC	169
tr E2CZS9 E2CZS9_9POXV	ITWFFISNDVSPGCYRIDVSKLEKLNK	YHCHNDPKDLFSNIPSRFE	VPRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr A0A881SY50 A0A881SY50_SWPV	ITWFFISNNISPEGCYSIDLKLEKINTQ	YHCHDDPKKHFNSVDRFD	IHRSYLFLDIEC	169
tr Q08FV4 Q08FV4_DPV83	ITWFFISNKISPEGCYTIDLEKMEKINNO	YHCHNDPKCEFT-PIRFRN	INRSYLFEDIEC	168
tr A0A3S7SVZ5 A0A3S7SVZ5_9POXV	ITWFFISNKISPEGCYTIDLEKMEKINNO	YHCHSDPKCEFT-PIRFRN	INRSYLFEDIEC	168
tr Q08FD4 Q08FD4_DPV84	ITWFFISNKISPEGCYTIDLEKMEKINNO	YHCHSDPKCEFT-PIRFRN	INRSYLFEDIEC	168

tr A0A0M3ZCQ4 A0A0M3ZCQ4_9POXV	DFSPATGLTF	TEIVMLNIMKRILEHRFD	ITFNGN	FD	RYIT	GRLEILEK	KFIYFSL	276
tr A0A068EE70 A0A068EE70_9POXV	DFSPKDRITY	TEVVMLLIMKKILEHRFD	VITFNGN	FD	RYIS	GRLEILEK	SFIYFSL	276
tr A0A2H4X2A1 A0A2H4X2A1_9POXV	DFSPKDRITY	TEVVMLLIMKKILEHRFD	VITFNGN	FD	RYIS	GRLEILEK	SFIYFSL	276
tr A0A7G0XLV5 A0A7G0XLV5_FOWPV	DFSPKDRITY	TEIVMLNIMKRILEHRFD	VITFNGN	FD	RYIS	GRLEILEK	SFIYFSL	276
sp P21402 DPOL_FOWFN	DFSPKDRITY	TEIVMLNIMKRILEHRFD	VITFNGN	FD	RYIS	GRLEILEK	SFIYFSL	276
tr A0A2C9DSJ8 A0A2C9DSJ8_9POXV	EFSPAQAVTF	SEILLLTIMKRVLEQRFD	VVTFNGN	FD	RYLS	GRLEIL	TRTQVIFRS	283
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	EFALEPGVTF	SEVVLQLAKRLLERHFD	VITFNGN	FD	RYVS	NRQLQL	TQSSVCFRL	283
tr Q8U249 Q8U249_9POXV	EFALEPGVTF	SEVVLQLAKRLLERHFD	VITFNGN	FD	RYVS	NRQLQL	TQSSVCFRL	283
sp Q84173 DPOL_ORFN2	DVKFDAEVTL	PEVTLRLVAKRLLLEPLDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYLD	SRLSLL	TGHEHIFRL	289
tr U3UBH8 U3UBH8_9POXV	EADLSREVVL	SEVVMQITRLLIESAFDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYVN	NRLELL	TGESVTFRL	286
tr A0A1U9H104 A0A1U9H104_9POXV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr A0A0K1LE69 A0A0K1LE69_9POXV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr A0A212PWR2 A0A212PWR2_COWPX	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr Q2QJ33 Q2QJ33_9POXV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr Q0G22 Q0G22_HSPV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr Q6R2N7 Q6R2N7_9POXV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr A0A2P1JPK6 A0A2P1JPK6_9POXV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr Q2QJ19 Q2QJ19_RACVI	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGDKIIFRS	288
tr Q2QJ70 Q2QJ70_9POXV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGDKIIFRS	288
tr Q2QJ71 Q2QJ71_9POXV	EMDYERELVL	SEIVLLQIAKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGDKIIFRS	288
tr A0A223FMP5 A0A223FMP5_9POXV	DMDYNEKYL	SEIVMLQISKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIT	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	289
tr G3EIC1 G3EIC1_9POXV	DMDYNEKYL	SEIVMLQISKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	289
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	DMDYNEKYL	SEIVMLQISKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr A0A7D0UGA2 A0A7D0UGA2_9POXV	ELDYKKEFIL	TEITMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	290
tr G0T3C8 G0T3C8_9POXV	ELDYKKEFIL	TEITMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	287
tr A0A1B2LPK1 A0A1B2LPK1_9POXV	DVDYTKI	SEITMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr A0A5C0PPQ2 A0A5C0PPQ2_9POXV	DVDYTKI	SEITMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr A0A1C9HHQ2 A0A1C9HHQ2_LSDV	DVDYTKI	SEITMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr A0A2H4EUX3 A0A2H4EUX3_SHEV	DVDYTKI	SEITMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr A0A2P1A9C0 A0A2P1A9C0_SHEV	DVDYTKI	SEITMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr E2C2S9 E2C2S9_9POXV	DVDYKKEFIL	TEITMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGERIIFRS	288
tr A0A881SY50 A0A881SY50_SWPV	DIDYKCEFIL	TEINMLKIAKMLLEQDF	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	288
tr Q08FV4 Q08FV4_DPV83	EMDYKKEFIL	SEIVMLQISKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	287
tr A0A3S7SVZ5 A0A3S7SVZ5_9POXV	EMDYKKEFIL	SEIVMLQISKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGKEIIFRS	287
tr Q08FD4 Q08FD4_DPV84	EMDYKKEFIL	SEIVMLQISKQLELTFDY	VVTFNGN	FD	RYIS	NRLELL	TGERIIFRS	287
:	:	:	:	:	:	:	:	:

tr A0A0M3ZCQ4 A0A0M3ZCQ4_9POXV	PDKSETIKLKI	FERFQS	---GGTF	NKTYH	NNNNG	AIF	FDLYAFIQ	TERLESYKLDN	332	
tr A0A068EE70 A0A068EE70_9POXV	PDATETVKLKI	FERFVT	---GGTF	NKTYH	NNNNG	VIF	FDLYAFIQ	TERLDSYKLDN	332	
tr A0A2H4X2A1 A0A2H4X2A1_9POXV	PDATETVKLKI	FERFVT	---GGTF	NKTYH	NNNNG	VIF	FDLYAFIQ	TERLDSYKLDN	332	
tr A0A7G0XLV5 A0A7G0XLV5_FOWPV	PDATETVKLKI	FERFVT	---GGTF	NKTYH	NNNNG	VIF	FDLYAFIQ	TERLDSYKLDN	332	
sp P21402 DPOL_FOWFN	PDATETVKLKI	FERFVT	---GGTF	NKTYH	NNNNG	VIF	FDLYAFIQ	TERLDSYKLDN	332	
tr A0A2C9DSJ8 A0A2C9DSJ8_9POXV	PDNSEAVL	LCIYERFLSSHRGPGG	YVA	NKTYH	NNNNG	VIF	FDLYGFIQ	TERLESYKLDN	343	
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	PDQREP	VKLVIYERSLASHRGAGGM	ANTS	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	KAERLDSYKLDN	343	
tr Q8U249 Q8U249_9POXV	PDQREP	VKLVIYERSLASHRGAGGM	ANTS	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	KAERLDSYKLDN	343	
sp Q84173 DPOL_ORFN2	PDGTE	TVNCVVERTKSSHKGVGG	S	TTPHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYAFIQ	TERLDSYKLDN	349	
tr U3UBH8 U3UBH8_9POXV	PDHSET	VKLVIYERNLSSHRGQGG	VA	NTTYH	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYYFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	356	
tr A0A1U9H104 A0A1U9H104_9POXV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A0K1LE69 A0A0K1LE69_9POXV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A212PWR2 A0A212PWR2_COWPX	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr Q2QJ33 Q2QJ33_9POXV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr Q0G22 Q0G22_HSPV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr Q6R2N7 Q6R2N7_9POXV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A2P1JPK6 A0A2P1JPK6_9POXV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr Q2QJ19 Q2QJ19_RACVI	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr Q2QJ70 Q2QJ70_9POXV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr Q2QJ71 Q2QJ71_9POXV	PDKKEAVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A223FMP5 A0A223FMP5_9POXV	PDKKESVH	LCIYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	349
tr G3EIC1 G3EIC1_9POXV	PDKKEHV	MLSVYERNQSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	349
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	PDKKETV	HMCIYERNLSSHKGACGV	S	NTTYH	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348	
tr A0A7D0UGA2 A0A7D0UGA2_9POXV	PDKEEMV	YLCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	350
tr G0T3C8 G0T3C8_9POXV	PDKKEI	VYLCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYSFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	347
tr A0A1B2LPK1 A0A1B2LPK1_9POXV	PDKKEHVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A5C0PPQ2 A0A5C0PPQ2_9POXV	PDKKEHVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A1C9HHQ2 A0A1C9HHQ2_LSDV	PDKKEHVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A2H4EUX3 A0A2H4EUX3_SHEV	PDKKEHVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A2P1A9C0 A0A2P1A9C0_SHEV	PDKKEHVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr E2C2S9 E2C2S9_9POXV	PDQREVVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr A0A881SY50 A0A881SY50_SWPV	PDQREVVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	348
tr Q08FV4 Q08FV4_DPV83	PDQREVVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	347
tr A0A3S7SVZ5 A0A3S7SVZ5_9POXV	PDQREVVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	347
tr Q08FD4 Q08FD4_DPV84	PDQREVVH	LCIYERNLSSHKGVGG	MA	NTT	PHV	NNNNG	TIF	FDLYTFIQ	SEKLDYKLDN	347
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	← EXO →	POL →					
tr A0A0M3ZCQ4 A0A0M3ZCQ4_9POXV	VNSKV	KYPYIGGKVFMP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCVVLSN	565	
tr A0A068EE70 A0A068EE70_9POXV	KITKV	RYPYIGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	566
tr A0A2H4X2A1 A0A2H4X2A1_9POXV	KITKV	RYPYIGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	566
tr A0A7G0XLV5 A0A7G0XLV5_FOWPV	KITKV	RYPYIGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	565
sp P21402 DPOL_FOWPN	KITKV	RYPYIGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	565
tr A0A2C9DSJ8 A0A2C9DSJ8_9POXV	SVSRT	RYPYIGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	580
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	TQEPA	RYPYIGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	576
tr Q8U249 Q8U249_9POXV	TQEPA	RYPYIGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	576
sp Q84173 DPOL_ORFN2	ADTKS	KFFYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	581
tr U3UBH8 U3UBH8_9POXV	NARKT	KFLYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	583
tr A0A1U9H104 A0A1U9H104_9POXV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	578
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VARV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	578
tr A0A0K1LE69 A0A0K1LE69_9POXV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr A0A212PWR2 A0A212PWR2_COWPX	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr Q2QJ3 Q2QJ3_9POXV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr Q0GP22 Q0GP22_HSPV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr Q6RZ7 Q6RZ7_9POXV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr A0A2P1JPK6 A0A2P1JPK6_9POXV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr Q2QJ19 Q2QJ19_RACVI	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr Q2QJ70 Q2QJ70_9POXV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr Q2QJ1 Q2QJ1_9POXV	SETKQ	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	579
tr A0A223FMP5 A0A223FMP5_9POXV	SNNKQ	KLYEYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	580
tr G3EIC1 G3EIC1_9POXV	YDTKQ	KLYEYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	581
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	TEKNN	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	580
tr A0A7D0UGA2 A0A7D0UGA2_9POXV	SEKNI	KYHYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	583
tr G0T3C8 G0T3C8_9POXV	SEKLA	KYHYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	580
tr A0A1B2LPK1 A0A1B2LPK1_9POXV	SEKKN	KYHYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	584
tr A0A5C0PQP2 A0A5C0PQP2_9POXV	SEKKN	KYHYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	584
tr A0A1C9HHQ2 A0A1C9HHQ2_LSDV	SEKKN	KYHYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	584
tr A0A2H4EUX3 A0A2H4EUX3_SHEV	SEKKN	KYHYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	584
tr A0A2P1A9C0 A0A2P1A9C0_SHEV	SEKKN	KYHYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	584
tr E2CZS9 E2CZS9_9POXV	SEKKN	KYHYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	580
tr A0A881SY50 A0A881SY50_SWPV	NGKKN	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	581
tr Q08FV4 Q08FV4_DPV83	NEKKN	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	582
tr A0A3S7SVZ5 A0A3S7SVZ5_9POXV	NEKKN	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	582
tr Q08FD4 Q08FD4_DPV84	NEKKN	KFPYEGGKVF	LP	SQKTFENNVMIF	YNSLYPNV	YVYANLSPETLVCIVLNTN	582

tr A0A0M3ZCQ4 A0A0M3ZCQ4_9POXV	LLKDATTIETALYDS	LYIKI	IANSVYGLMGFNNSILYSYSSAK	CTTIGRNMIMYLD	685
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tr A0A2H4X2A1 A0A2H4X2A1_9POXV	LLKTASTTIEITLYDS	LYIKI	IANSVYGLMGFNNSILYSYSSAK	CTTIGRNMITYLD	686
tr A0A7G0XLV5 A0A7G0XLV5_FOWPV	LLKTASTTIEITLYDS	LYIKI	IANSVYGLMGFNNSILYSYSSAK	CTTIGRNMITYLD	685
sp P21402 DPOL_FOWPN	LLKTASTTIEITLYDS	LYIKI	IANSVYGLMGFNNSILYSYSSAK	CTTIGRNMITYLD	685
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tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	LMRAASSGLERTLYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFYNSSLYSSAK	CTTIGRVMITYLD	696
tr Q8U249 Q8U249_9POXV	LMRAASSGLERTLYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFYNSSLYSSAK	CTTIGRVMITYLD	696
sp Q84173 DPOL_ORFN2	LMKAAETAVDREIYNS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMIAYLE	701
tr U3UBH8 U3UBH8_9POXV	LMKSASGPIERGIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMIAYLE	703
tr A0A1U9H104 A0A1U9H104_9POXV	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	699
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	698
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VARV	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	698
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tr A0A212PWR2 A0A212PWR2_COWPX	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	699
tr Q2QJ3 Q2QJ3_9POXV	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	699
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	699
tr Q0GP22 Q0GP22_HSPV	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	699
tr Q6RZ7 Q6RZ7_9POXV	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	699
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	MLKQATSSTEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	699
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tr G3EIC1 G3EIC1_9POXV	MMKHATTSTEKDIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLE	701
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tr A0A2H4EUX3 A0A2H4EUX3_SHEV	KYKEATLSTDKSIYNS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLN	704
tr A0A2P1A9C0 A0A2P1A9C0_SHEV	KYKEATLSTDKSIYNS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLN	704
tr E2CZS9 E2CZS9_9POXV	MKETNDVVEKAIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLN	700
tr A0A881SY50 A0A881SY50_SWPV	LLKQSTNLTDKSIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLN	701
tr Q08FV4 Q08FV4_DPV83	LLKQATDSTEKSIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLN	702
tr A0A3S7SVZ5 A0A3S7SVZ5_9POXV	LLKQATDSTEKSIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLN	702
tr Q08FD4 Q08FD4_DPV84	LLKQATDSTEKSIYDS	MYTYKI	IANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSSAK	CTTIGRMMIYLN	702

//End of poxviral pols sequences		
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tx A0A068EE70 A0A068EE70__SPOXV	VFFSRLFGTKPVSFSSD	9888
tx A0A2H4X2A1 A0A2H4X2A1__SPOXV	LFFSRLFGTKPVSFSSD	9888
tx A0A7G0XLV5 A0A7G0XLV5__FOWFPV	LFFIIRLFGTKPVSFSSD	9888
sp P21402 DPOL_FOWPN	LFFSRLFGTKPVSFSSD	9888
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tx A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5__MCV2	EFFTRLFGVRFVFSN-	10004
tx Q8U249 Q8U249__SPOXV	EFFTRLFGVRFVFSN-	10004
sp Q84173 DPOL_ORFN2	LFERLFGSRPVSFTS-	10008
tx U3UBH8 U3UBH8__SPOXV	QFFTRLFGTRPLFYD-	10007
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tx A0A212PWR2 A0A212PWR2__COWPXP	SFFERMFGSKPTFYEA	10006
tx Q2QJ3 Q2QJ3__SPOXV	SFFERMFGSRPTFYEA	10006
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	SFFORMFSGSRPTFYEA	10006
tx Q0GP22 Q0GP22__HSPV	SFFERMFGSKPTFYEA	10006
tx Q6RZN7 Q6RZN7__SPOXV	SFFERMFGSKPTFYEA	10006
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tx Q2QJ11 Q2QJ11__SPOXV	SFFERMFGSRPTFYE-	10005
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tx G3EIC1 G3EIC1__SPOXV	SFFORMFSGTKPIFYK-	10008
tx Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3__YMTVS	SFFERMFGTKPIFYK-	10006
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tx G0T3C8 G0T3C8__SPOXV	SFFEKMFSGTRPIFYK-	10006
tx A0A1B2LPK1 A0A1B2LPK1__SPOXV	SFFEKMFSGTRPIFYK-	10010
tx A0A5C0PQP2 A0A5C0PQP2__SPOXV	SFFEKMFSGTRPIFYK-	10010
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tx A0A2H4EUX3 A0A2H4EUX3__SHEV	SFFEKMFSGTRPIFYK-	10010
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tx E2CZS9 E2CZS9__SPOXV	SFFEKMFSGTRPIFYK-	10006
tx A0A881SY50 A0A881SY50__SWPV	SFFEKLFSGSRPIFYK-	10008
tx Q08FV4 Q08FV4__DPVS3	SFFEKMFSGTKPIFYK-	10010
tx A0A3S7SVZ5 A0A3S7SVZ5__SPOXV	SFFEKMFSGTKPIFYK-	10010
tx Q08FD4 Q08FD4__DPVS4	SFFEKMFSGTKPIFYK-	10011

A0A0M3ZCQ4, Turkeypox virus	A0A068EE 70, Pigeonpox virus
A0A2H4X2A1, Flamingopox virus	A0A7G0XLV5, Fowlpox virus
P21402, Fowlpox virus	A0A2C9DSJ8, Western grey kangaropox virus
A0A1S7DLM5, Molluscum contagiosum virus	Q8U249, Molluscum contagiosum virus
Q84173, Orf virus	U3UBH8, Squirrelpox virus
A0A1U9H104, Orthopoxvirus Tena Dona	P0DOO5, Variola virus (isolate Human/India)
P0DOO6, Variola virus	A0A0K1LE69, Camelopox virus
A0A212PWR2, Cowpox virus	Q2QJ3, Taterapox virus
A0A7H0DN44, Monkeypox virus	Q0GP22, Horsepox virus, Q6RZN7, Rabbitpox virus
O57191, Vaccinia virus (strain Ankara)	A0A2P1JPK6, Buffalopox virus
Q2QJ19, Raccoon poxvirus	Q2QJ10, Volepox virus
Q2QJ11, Skunkpox virus	A0A223FMP5, Murmansk poxvirus
G3EIC1, Yokapox virus	Q6TUX3, Yaba monkey tumor virus
A0A7D0UGA2, Brazilian porcupinepox virus 1	G0T3C8, Cotia virus
A0A1B2LPK1, Goatpox virus	A0A5C0PQP2, Goatpox virus
A0A1C9HHQ2, Lumpy skin disease virus	A0A2H4EUX3, Sheeppox virus
A0A2P1A9C0, Sheeppox virus	E2CZS9, Myxoma virus
A0A881SY50, Swinepox virus	Q08FV4, Deerpox virus (strain Mule deer)
A0A3S7SVZ5, Moosepox virus	Q08FD4, Deerpox virus

Figure 3 MSA of different poxviral replicative DNA polymerase catalytic subunits

Figure 4 Structure of HHN endonuclease motif showing the invariant active site amino acids and the approximate distances between them

HHN motif has been identified in hundreds of prokaryotic and eukaryotic organisms and is known to involve in many important functions like, DNA homing, restriction, repair, chromosome degradation, etc. One of the main functions of these endonucleases is to promote the lateral transfer of their own coding and flanking DNA regions between genomes, by a recombination-dependent process known as 'homing'. Importantly, unlike restriction enzymes, these homing endonucleases have a very long recognition sequence of ~20 amino acids to prevent random cleaving of the host genome. Some of the -HHN- motifs are free-standing and some are embedded in other genes [39].

The poxviral DNA pol apoenzyme with its processive factor and UDG form the active holoenzyme (Figs. 1A & 1B). The structure of the holoenzyme from the mpox virus has been extensively studied by cryo-EM technique by Peng *et al.* [27]

and Wang *et al.* [28]. They found that the D⁵⁴⁹ and D⁷⁵³, together with the triphosphate tail of dTTP coordinated one divalent metal ion, possibly the catalytic Mg²⁺ (highlighted in dark green). Therefore, the two invariant Ds, viz. D⁵⁴⁹ and D⁷⁵³ of poxviral DNA pols could be equivalent to the two invariant Ds (D⁷⁰⁵ and D⁸⁸²) which coordinate β- and γ-phosphates of the incoming dNTP in the DNA pol I of *E. coli* [40]. Furthermore, Peng *et al.* [27] found the ribose of dTTP stacks on top of the phenyl ring of Y⁵⁵⁴ from the palm domain, which is critical to discriminating against ribonucleotides by providing a steric hindrance to the ribonucleotide-specific 2'-OH. Interestingly, the present MSA analysis locates that the base discriminating amino acid Y⁵⁵⁴ in one of the characteristic motifs, -SLY⁵⁵⁴PN-, found in the poxvirus DNA pols including the mpox, variola and vaccinia and also found in other B-family pols [37]. The positively charged R⁶³⁴ and K⁶⁶¹ of the fingers' domain are found closer to the active site, where they could interact with the triphosphate group of incoming dNTPs. In fact, the K⁶⁶¹ is found in the proposed mpox, variola and vaccinia viral DNA pol active sites, -⁶⁵⁶MQ⁴YTYK⁶⁶¹IVANSVY⁸GL- (Table 3) and proposed as the proton abstractor to initiate the catalysis. Table 3 shows the similarity among the DNA pol active sites of the replicative pols from both pro- and eukaryotes.

It is suggested that some crucial mutations in viral proteins may alter the phenotype and pathogenicity of the viral strains. The F8L mutation (L¹⁰⁸→F) which emerged in 2022, is suggested to be a potential contributing factor to the 2022 mpox outbreak (highlighted in light magenta). The present analysis shows that the L¹⁰⁸→F mutation is located in the NTD (not in the PR exonuclease or pol domains) of the mpox virus DNA pol and conserved in most of the poxviral pols with few exceptions and hence, possibly involve with its interaction with the processivity factor. Similarly, the CDV resistance observed in VACV DNA pol is achieved by A³¹⁴→T and A⁶⁸⁴→V mutations in E9 DNA pol catalytic subunit. Both A³¹⁴ and A⁶⁸⁴ are conserved in mpox virus also. The present study identifies the VACV pol mutation, A³¹⁴→T within the PR exonuclease domain (highlighted in light magenta) and interestingly, is not conserved in all poxviral DNA pols. However, the second mutation, A⁶⁸⁴→V is completely conserved in all poxvirus DNA pols including the mpox virus (highlighted in light magenta) and is located downstream of the pol catalytic core. These results suggest that these mutations do not alter any of the active site amino acids in the PR exonuclease and pol domains, but by simply altering the residues close to the active sites of the enzyme, block the binding of the DNA pol inhibitor, CDV, and make the virus resistant to CDV. Kannan *et al.* [41] have suggested that the A³¹⁴→T mutation could interfere with the shuttling of primer to the PR exonuclease domain (as it is located within the PR exonuclease domain), whereas A⁶⁸⁴→V is likely to interfere with template positioning (as it is located in the 'palm' subdomain), which could alter the CDV-pp binding at the dCTP-binding pocket.

3.2. Conservation of the polymerase catalytic core region

Table 3 shows a detailed analysis of the polymerization active site core regions of different pols from bacteria, bacteriophages, smallpox, vaccinia, mpox viruses, yeast, plant and animal. The polymerization active site amino acids are arrived at both from the sequence similarities and from the experimentally confirmed ones (highlighted in dark blue). High similarity among the pol catalytic cores suggests that most of the nucleotide pols not only share a common 3D structure of their pol domains (exhibiting palm, fingers and thumb subdomains), but also very similar catalytic core. It is clear from the table that the A-family (Pol I) and C-family (Pol III) DNA pols do not possess the -SLYPS- and -YGD TDS motifs and only the B-family pols possess the two invariant motifs. It is interesting to note that even among the B-family pols, the ε pols from different sources also do not possess these two characteristic motifs (Table 3).

Table 3 Polymerase active site catalytic core regions and presence/absence of SYLPS/N and YGDTDS motifs in DNA pols from smallpox, vaccinia, mpox viruses and plant, animal, bacteria and bacteriophages

DNA pol	Polymerization Active Site	-SLYPS- & -YGDTDS-
Smallpox virus	- ⁶⁴⁷ TEKAIYDSMQ ⁻⁴ YTYK ⁶⁶⁰ IANSVY ⁸ GLM-	- ⁵⁵¹ SLYPSN-/-YGDTDS-
Vaccinia virus	- ⁶⁴⁸ TEKAIYDSMQ ⁻⁴ YTYK ⁶⁶¹ IVANSVY ⁸ GLM-	- ⁵⁵² SLYPSN-/-YGDTDS-
Mpox virus	- ⁶⁴⁸ TEKAIYDSMQ ⁻⁴ YTYK ⁶⁶⁶ IVANSVY ⁸ GLM-	- ⁵⁵² SLYPSN-/-YGDTDS-
Yeast α pol (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	- ⁹³¹ HKRVQCDIRQ ⁻⁴ QALK ⁹⁴⁴ L TANSMY ⁸ C ⁹⁵³ CL-	- ⁷⁵⁶ SLYPS-/-YGDTDS-
Plant α pol (<i>A. thaliana</i>)	- ⁹⁸⁰ LKYWELDIRQ ⁻⁴ QALK ⁹⁹³ L TANSMY ⁸ GCL-	- ⁹²¹ SLYPS-/-YGDTDS-
Animal α pol (Humans)	- ⁹³⁷ DLILQYDIRQ ⁻⁴ KALK ⁹⁵⁰ L TANSMY ⁸ GCL-	- ⁸⁶³ SLYPS-/-YGDTDS-
Yeast ϵ pol (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	- ⁷⁹⁷ MIVLYDSLQ ⁻⁴ LAHK ⁸⁰⁹ VILNSFY ⁸ GYV-	Nil/Nil
Plant ϵ pol (<i>A. thaliana</i>)	- ⁷⁷⁰ MVVVYDSLQ ⁻⁴ LAHK ⁷⁸² CILNSFY ⁸ GYV-	Nil/Nil
Animal ϵ pol (Humans)	- ⁸¹² MEVLYDSLQ ⁻⁴ LAHK ⁸²⁴ CILNSFY ⁸ GYV-	Nil/Nil
Yeast δ pol (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	- ⁶⁸⁸ FKRDVLDNGRQ ⁻⁴ LALK ⁷⁰¹ ISANSVY ⁸ GFT-	- ⁶¹¹ SLYPS-/-YGDTDS-
Plant δ pol (<i>A. thaliana</i>)	- ⁶⁷⁹ LEKAVLDNGRQ ⁻⁴ LALK ⁶⁹² ISANSVY ⁸ GFT-	- ⁶⁰³ SLYPS-/-YGDTDS-
Animal δ pol (Humans)	- ⁶⁸¹ LRROVLDNGRQ ⁻⁴ LALK ⁶⁹⁴ VSANSVY ⁸ GFT-	- ⁶⁰⁵ SLYPS-/-YGDTDS-
DNA pol I (<i>E. coli</i>) [@]	- ⁷⁴⁵ PLETVTSEQR ⁷⁵⁸ RSALK ⁷⁵⁸ AIN ⁷⁶⁶ GLIY ⁸ GMS-	Nil/Nil
<i>Taq</i> DNA pol I (<i>T. aquaticus</i>)	- ⁶⁵⁰ PREAVDPLMR ⁶⁵⁹ RAAK ⁶⁶³ TINFGVLY ⁹ GM-	Nil/Nil
DNA pol II (<i>E. coli</i>) [@]	- ⁴⁸⁰ AKRQGNKPLS ⁻⁴ QALK ⁴⁹³ IMNAFY ⁸ GVL-	- ⁴²² SLYPS-/-YGDTDS-
DNA pol III (Replicase, <i>E. coli</i>)	- ⁶⁶¹ ISYPDVQWQH ⁻⁴ ESLK ⁶⁷⁴ PVLEPTY ⁸ GII-	Nil/Nil
DNA pol (T7 bacteriophage)	- ⁵⁰⁹ NQIAAELPTR ⁻⁴ DNAK ⁵²³ TFIY ⁸ GFLY ⁹ GAG-	Nil/Nil

[@] DNA pol I and II are not the replicative pols, but only the pol II possesses the two typical conserved motifs, -SLYPS- and -YGDTDS- suggesting possible different evolutionary origins. However, these two motifs are not also found in the replicative pol III of *E. coli* and eukaryotic replicative ϵ pols.

The confirmed active site amino acids (by SDM and active site-directed labelling) are highlighted in dark blue. In the *E. coli* pol I, the replacement of K⁷⁵⁸ with A⁷⁵⁸ caused a 1,000-fold reduction in k_{cat} . In *Taq* pol I, R⁶⁵⁹ and K⁶⁶³ were immutable [42].

The Ala substitutions in the *E. coli* pol I resulted in moderate to severe effects on the pol I activity of the individual mutant enzymes. Severe loss of activity was associated with R⁷⁵⁴→A, K⁷⁵⁸→A, F⁷⁶²→A, and Y⁷⁶⁶→A (highlighted in dark blue) [43].

3.3. Conservation of PR exonuclease active site domain in DNA polymerases

DNA replicases replicate the genomes with very high fidelity. However, during their incredibly high-speed polymerization reactions (~100 nt in eukaryotes to ~1000 nt in prokaryotes per second), mistakes do happen and the pols sometimes insert the wrong nucleotide or sometimes skip a nucleotide or add a nucleotide into the sequence. Almost all of these mistakes are fixed meticulously through different DNA repair enzymes associated with genome replications. For example, most of the mistakes are corrected immediately during the replication process itself through the PR exonucleases associated or part of the DNA replicases.

Table 4 DEDD-superfamily of PR exonuclease active site amino acids of the replicative DNA pols from viral and pro- and eukaryotic sources

Organism	PR exonuclease active site structure
Prokaryotic DEDD family PR Exonuclease Active Site Structure	
<i>E. coli</i> DNA Pol I	-D ³⁵⁵ TE ³⁵⁷ -----Y ⁴²⁴ -----Y ⁴⁹⁷ -----D ⁵⁰¹ -
<i>E. coli</i> DNA Pol II	-D ¹⁵⁶ TE ¹⁵⁸ -----FD ²²⁹ -----Y ³³¹ -----D ³³⁵ -
<i>E. coli</i> DNA Pol III (Replicase, ε-subunit)	-D ¹² TE ¹⁴ -----FD ¹⁰³ -----Y ¹⁶² -----D ¹⁶⁷ -
<i>Tth</i> DNA pol III (Replicase, ε-subunit)	-D ⁷⁷ LE-----FD ¹⁶¹ -----H ²¹⁴ -----D ²¹⁹ -
Mitochondrial DNA Polymerase γ from Yeasts, Plants and Animals	
Yeasts (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	-D ¹⁷¹ VE ¹⁷³ -----YD ²³⁰ -----Y ³⁴³ -----D ³⁴⁷ -
Plants (<i>A. thaliana</i> DNA pol IA, Mitochondria/Chplastic)	-D ³⁹⁴ TE ³⁹⁶ -----FD ³⁹⁹ -----Y ⁴⁷⁰ -----D ⁴⁷⁴ -
Plants (<i>A. thaliana</i> DNA pol IB, Mitochondria/Chplastic)	-D ¹⁷² TE ¹⁷⁴ -----FD ¹⁴⁸ -----Y ¹⁴⁸ -----D ¹⁵² -
Animals (<i>Homo sapiens</i>)	-D ¹⁹⁸ VE ²⁰⁰ -----FD ²⁷⁴ -----Y ³⁹⁵ -----D ³⁹⁹ -
Eukaryotic δ and ε Nuclear DNA Polymerases from Yeasts, Plants and Animals	
Yeasts (<i>S. cerevisiae</i> δ DNA pol)	-D ³²³ IE ³²³ -----FD ⁴⁰⁷ -----Y ⁵¹⁶ -----D ⁵²⁰ -/ ε pol-D ²⁹² IE ²⁹² -----FD ³⁸³ -----Y ⁴⁷³ -----D ⁴⁷⁷ -
Plants (<i>A. thaliana</i> δ DNA pol)	-D ³¹⁴ IE ³¹⁴ -----FD ³⁹⁶ -----Y ⁵⁰⁷ -----D ⁵¹¹ -/ ε pol-D ²⁴⁹ IE ²⁴⁹ -----FD ³⁴⁰ -----Y ⁴³¹ -----D ⁴³⁵ -
Animals (<i>H. sapiens</i> δ DNA pol)	-D ³¹⁶ IE ³¹⁸ -----FD ⁴⁰² -----Y ⁵¹¹ -----D ⁵¹⁵ -/ ε pol-D ²⁷⁵ IE ²⁷⁷ -----F ³⁶⁷ D ³⁶⁸ -----Y ⁴⁵⁸ S ⁴⁵⁹ -----D ⁴⁶² -
Nuclear-encoded Organellar Eukaryotic RNA Polymerases from Yeasts, Plants and Animals	
Plants (<i>A. thaliana</i> , NE-RNA pol, Chplast)	-D ⁹⁴⁸ VE-----LD ⁹⁷³ F-----NH ⁹⁸⁶ L-----D ⁹⁹⁰ LC-
Plants (<i>A. thaliana</i> , NE-RNA pol, Mito)	-D ⁹³⁷ IE-----VD ⁹⁶⁶ F-----NH ⁹⁶⁹ L-----D ⁹⁷³ LC-
Animals (<i>H. sapiens</i> , NE-RNA pol, Mito)	-D ⁵⁴⁰ AE-----MD ⁸⁰¹ F-----NH ⁸¹⁵ L-----D ⁸¹⁹ VA
DEDD family PR Exonuclease Active Site Structures in Viral Polymerases (DdDp/RdRp)	
T4 Phage (DNA pol)	-D ¹¹² IE ¹¹⁴ -----FD ²¹⁹ -----Y ³²⁰ -----D ³²⁴ -
(Ds DNA) Smallpox Virus (DdRp)	-D ¹⁶⁶ IE-----FD ²⁶⁸ -----Y ⁴⁵⁷ -----D ⁴⁶¹ -
(Ds DNA) Vaccinia Virus (DdRp)	-D ¹⁶⁶ IE-----FD ²⁶⁸ -----Y ⁴⁵⁸ -----D ⁴⁶² -
(Ds DNA) Mpox Virus (DdRp)	-D ¹⁶⁶ IE-----FD ²⁶⁸ -----Y ⁴⁵⁸ -----D ⁴⁶² -
Human Herpes Simplex Virus (DdDp)	-D ³⁶⁸ IE-----FD ⁴⁷¹ -----Y ⁵⁷⁷ -----D ⁵⁸¹ -
(+ RNA) SARS-CoV-1 (#NSP14) (RdRp)*	-D ⁹⁰ VE ⁹² -----FD ¹⁹¹ -----Y ²⁶⁸ -----D ²⁷³ -
(+ RNA) MERS-CoV (#NSP14) (RdRp)*	-D ⁹⁰ VE ⁹² -----FD ¹⁹¹ -----Y ²⁶⁸ -----D ²⁷³ -
(+ RNA) SARS-CoV-2 (#NSP14) (RdRp)*	-D ⁹⁰ VE ⁹² -----FD ¹⁹¹ -----Y ²⁶⁸ -----D ²⁷³ -
(- RNA) Human Influenza Virus A: H1N1 (PA subunit)	-D ³⁴⁷ IE-----LD ⁴²⁵ -----H ⁵¹⁰ -----D ⁵¹⁴ -
(- RNA) Human Influenza Virus B (PA subunit)	-D ¹⁹⁴ IE-----LD ⁴²⁰ -----H ⁵⁰⁶ -----D ⁵¹⁰ -
(- RNA) Human Influenza Virus C (PA subunit)	-D ⁸⁴ LE-----LD ²⁸⁸ -----H ⁴⁹⁴ -----D ⁴⁹⁸ -
(- RNA) Human Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RdRp)	-D ⁶⁶⁴ LE-----LD ⁷⁹⁴ -----H ⁸²⁹ -----D ⁸³³ -
(- RNA) Nipah Virus (RdRp)	-D ¹¹⁰¹ LE-----LD ¹³⁷⁸ -----H ¹⁵¹⁸ -----D ¹⁵²² -
(- RNA) Ebola Virus (RdRp)	-D ⁶³² LE-----FD ⁸³¹ -----H ¹⁰⁰⁶ -----D ¹⁰¹⁰ -
(+ RNA) Hepatitis A Virus (RdRp)	-D ²³³ LE-----FD ³⁶³ -----Y ⁴⁸³ -----D ⁴⁸⁷ -

Eukaryotic replicative α pols (DNA primases) lack the PR exo active site.

Tth, *Thermus thermophilus*; NE, Nuclear encoded; Chplast, Chloroplast; Mito, Mitochondria;

The confirmed PR exo active site amino acids (by SDM and Crystallography) are highlighted in dark blue/light blue, respectively.;

*All possess the same PR exonuclease domain and their active site amino acids are completely conserved in Bat-RaTG13, Pangolin, Civet, SARS-CoV-1, MERS-CoV, SARS-CoV2 and HCoV-NL63.

#NSP14 is a multifunctional enzyme with two distinct activities, an N-terminal 3'→5' exoribonuclease (ExoN) and a C-terminal N7-methyltransferase (N7-MTase), both are crucial for lifecycle of the coronaviruses, indicating NSP14 as one of the prominent targets for the development of antiviral drugs.

In DNA replicases a wrong addition stalls the pol and the PR exonuclease active site moves in and removes the wrong nucleotide and allowing the pol to proceed. Thus, the PR exo and pol activities undergo polymerase-to-exonuclease and exonuclease-to-polymerase active site switching during the replication process without having the DNA pol to be disassociated from template DNA every time. The rest of the mistakes are corrected by a process known as mismatch repair after the replication. The incorrectly base-paired nucleotides cause deformities in the secondary structure of the final DNA molecule. The mismatch repair enzymes recognize these deformities and fix them by removing the incorrectly paired nucleotide and replacing it with the correct nucleotide. However, some replication errors make it past these repair mechanisms and thus, become permanent mutations. Such altered nucleotide sequences can then be passed down from one generation to the next, if they occur in cells that give rise to gametes. When the genes for the DNA repair enzymes themselves become mutated, replication mistakes begin accumulating at an alarmingly higher rate and such mutations can lead to many types of cancer in animals. It should also be noted that if the DNA repair were perfect and no mutations ever accumulated, there would be no genetic variation(s) and, in fact, these variations serve as the basis for the evolution of new variants. Table 4 shows the conservation of the PR exonuclease active site amino acids from

viruses to animals and plants. These PR exonucleases are classified under –DEDD- superfamily of exonucleases and they use either an Y or H as a proton acceptor from the metal-activated water molecule in the active site during the PR reactions [40].

3.4. ‘Mix and Match’ MSA of the replicative pols from 5 different sources, viz. bacteria, bacteriophages, poxviruses, plants and animals

Figure 5 shows the ‘mix and match’ MSA analysis of various replicative pols. The replicative pols analyzed include from 5 different sources, viz. bacteria, bacteriophages, poxviruses, plants and animals and are highlighted in different colours. Interestingly, they revealed both similarities and differences between them. The N-terminal regions are not aligned and show lots of gaps indicating poor conservations among them. Even the first completely conserved triad -DIE- of the PR exonuclease domain is also not aligned in all, i.e., the distance conservation is not maintained between bacteria and bacteriophages and the rest. However, the next three PR exonuclease active site amino acids are completely conserved and aligned in all (highlighted). In contrast, the active site amino acids in the pol domain are almost completely conserved and aligned in all. Interestingly, all the three catalytic Ds in the pol domain are completely conserved in all pols (highlighted in dark green). The proposed, highly conserved –HNNH- endonuclease motif is found only in the poxvirus DNA pols (highlighted), making the poxviral pols different from others. Similarly, the characteristic regulatory ZBMs invariably found at the CTDs of the eukaryotic replicative pols (α, δ and ε) are found only in plant and animal replicative pols (highlighted) and not in poxviral pols.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) Mix and Match MSA analysis of the replicative DNA pols from bacteriophages, bacteria, poxviruses, plants and animals.

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	---QGVTVYEADVRRPE-RYL-----MERFITAPVWL-----	126
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	---NGVTVYEGDVRPPE-RYL-----MERFITAPVWV-----	126
tr AOA5Y2S1M3 AOA5Y2S1M3_SALER	---NGVTVYEVADVRRPE-RYL-----MERFITSPVWI-----	126
tr AOA2B7LWU5 AOA2B7LWU5_9ESCH	---AGVTVYEVADVRRPE-RYL-----MERFITAPVWV-----	126
tr B7LV11 B7LV11_ESCF3	---AGVTVYEVADVRRPE-RYL-----MERFITSPVWV-----	126
tr AOA6N3R803 AOA6N3R803_SHIFL	---GGVTVYEVADVRRPE-RYL-----MERFITSPVWV-----	126
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	---GGVTVYEVADVRRPE-RYL-----MERFITSPVWV-----	126
tr AOA3P6LPK6 AOA3P6LPK6_SHIDY	---GGVTVYEVADVRRPE-RYL-----MERFITSPVWV-----	126
tr AOA0K0QSA0 AOA0K0QSA0_9CAUD	-----ASLDIEVTAP--EFPDPR-----	126
tr AOA1W5POA4 AOA1W5POA4_9CAUD	-----ASLDIEVTAP--EFPDPR-----	126
tr AOA7U3VGB5 AOA7U3VGB5_9CAUD	-----ANCDIEVTAG--EFPDPT-----	125
tr AOA5Q2F6H2 AOA5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	-----ANCDIEVTAS--QFPDPMKAEYE-----	129
tr AOA2K9VME2 AOA2K9VME2_9CAUD	-----ANCDIEVTGD--KFPDPMKAEYEIDAITHYDSIDDRFYVFDLL-----	149
tr AOA249XWD5 AOA249XWD5_9CAUD	-----ANCDIEVTGD--KFPDPMKAEYEI-----	130
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	-----ANCDIEVTGD--KFPDPMKAEYEI-----	130
tr AOA2U7NJH8 AOA2U7NJH8_9CAUD	-----CNVDIEFTSPI-GFPDPK-----	123
tr AOA0B5A2H2 AOA0B5A2H2_9CAUD	-----VNYDIEVTAP--EFPNAS-----	124
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	-----ANFDIEVTSPD-GFPEPS-----	127
tr AOA1Z1LY62 AOA1Z1LY62_9CAUD	-----ANCDIEVTAP--EFPDPS-----	126
tr AOA1S7DLM5 AOA1S7DLM5_MCV2	IEPNGCYRVFDAB-----L-----EPVRCARCFHCA----APRRAFATR	152
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	VCPDGCYVIDIKM-----L-----EKINDNCYHCN----DPQQLFLNP	152
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	ISPDGCYSLDDQY-----L-----TKINNGCYHCG----DPRNCFKAE	152
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VARV	ISPDGCYSLDDQY-----L-----TKINNGCYHCG----DPRNCFKAE	152
sp AOA7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	ISPDGCYSLDEQY-----L-----TKINNGCYHCD----DPRNCFKAE	152
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	ISPDGCYSLDEQY-----L-----TKINNGCYHCD----DPRNCFKAK	152
tr AOA287NEC0 AOA287NEC0_HORVV	--PAGKYRKAT-----RVMSY-----CQLELDCLYSDLVSHAPEGEYSK-	328
tr AOA3B6JHK9 AOA3B6JHK9_WHEAT	--PAGKYRKAT-----RVMSY-----CQLELDCLYSDLVSHAPEGEYSK-	308
tr AOA1D6QLT8 AOA1D6QLT8_MAIZE	--PAGKYRKA-----CIMS-----CQLELDCLYSDLVSHAPEGEYSK-	308
sp Q9LRE6 DPD1_ORYSJ	--PAGKYMKA-----RIMS-----CQLELDCLYSDLVSHAPEGEYSK-	310
sp Q9LVN7 DPD1_ARATH	---PTGKYKKA-----RTLSY-----CQLEFHCLYSDLVSHAPEGEYSK-	302
tr AOA078I2E2 AOA078I2E2_BRANA	--PAGKYKKA-----RTLSY-----CQLEFHCLYSDLVSHAPEGEYSK-	297
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	--PAGKYRVRKESQDEEPSKDNPSKVS-----AQIEVDISWADLISHPPEGEWQK-	310
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	--PAGKYVRAEK-----KATL-----CQLEVDVLSVDVISHPPEGEWQK-	302
sp P52431 DPD1_MOUSE	--PAGKYVRAEK-----KATL-----CQLEVDVLSVDVISHPPEGEWQK-	304
sp P28340 DPD1_HUMAN	--PAGKYALRLKE-----KATQ-----CQLEADVLSVDVISHPPEGEWQK-	306
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	--PAGKYVLRPKG-----KTTL-----CQLEADVLSVDVISHPPEGEWQK-	306
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	--PAGKYLLRLEG-----KATH-----CQLEADVLSVDVISHPPEGEWQK-	306
tr AOA5G2QET9 AOA5G2QET9_PIG	--PAGKYLLRPEG-----KATL-----CQLEADVLSVDVISHPPEGEWQK-	306
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	--PAGKYILRPEG-----KATL-----CQLEADVLSVDVISHPPEGEWQK-	305

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	-EGDTKDGAIVNARLKPDPYRPLKQVSLDIETTR-----HGELYCIGLEGC--G---	174
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	-DGEARDGALVNARLKPDPYRPLRWLSDIETTR-----HGELYCIGLEGC--G---	174
tr A0A5Y2S1M3 A0A5Y2S1M3_SALER	-DGEMRNGVIRNARLKPDPYRPLKQVSLDIETTR-----HGELYCIGLEGC--G---	174
tr A0A2B7LUW5 A0A2B7LUW5_9ESCH	-DGDFRDGAIVNARLKPDPYRPLKQVSLDIETTR-----HGELYCIGLEGC--G---	174
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	-EGDMHNGAIVNARLKPDPYRPLKQVSLDIETTR-----HGELYCIGLEGC--G---	174
tr A0A6N3R803 A0A6N3R803_SHIFL	-EGDMHNGTIVNARLKPDPYRPLKQVSLDIETTR-----HGELYCIGLEGC--G---	174
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	-EGDMHNGTIVNARLKPDPYRPLKQVSLDIETTR-----HGELYCIGLEGC--G---	174
tr A0A3P6LPK6 A0A3P6LPK6_SHIDY	-EGDMHNGTIVNARLKPDPYRPLKQVSLDIETTR-----HGELYCIGLEGC--G---	174
tr A0A0K0QSA0 A0A0K0QSA0_9CAUD	-----EAKYIDAITH-YDSVEDKFFVYDLVE---GGLD	156
tr A0A1W5POA4 A0A1W5POA4_9CAUD	-----EAKYIDAITH-YDSVEDKFFVYDLVE---GGLD	156
tr A0A7U3VGB5 A0A7U3VGB5_9CAUD	-----FAKYEIDAITH-YDSIEDKYFVFDLLNSARGRVT	158
tr A0A5Q2F6H2 A0A5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	-----IDAITH-YDSVDDKFFVFDLLHSLYGSVS	157
tr A0A2K9VME2 A0A2K9VME2_9CAUD	---NSMYGVRVANCDIEVTGDKFPDMKAEYEIDAITH-YDSIDDRFYVFDLLNSMYGSVS	206
tr A0A249XWD5 A0A249XWD5_9CAUD	-----DAITH-YDSIDDRFYVFDLLNSMYGSVS	157
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	-----DAITH-YDSIDDRFYVFDLLNSMYGSVS	157
tr A0A2U7NJH8 A0A2U7NJH8_9CAUD	-----AALHPIDAITH-YDSIDDKFYVFDLLHSPYGNVT	156
tr A0A0B5A2H2 A0A0B5A2H2_9CAUD	-----QALYPVDALH-YDSVANKFYVFDLLNSPYGSVT	157
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	-----QAKHPIDAITH-YDSIDDRFYVFDLLNSPYGNVT	160
tr A0A1Z1LY62 A0A1Z1LY62_9CAUD	-----QALYPIDAITH-YDSIDDRFYVFDLLNSPYGSVT	159
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	VPLFEVHTYLYFDIECQFDK-KFPSVFNPNVSHISFCVDRLGTEVRFSLINS--DLLP	209
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	IPKFDVSRSLYFDIECHFDK-KFPSVFNPNVSHVSCCVNLFGRLEKFTLINR--DMLS	209
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	IPRFDIPRSYLFIDIECHFDK-KFPSVFNPNISHTSYCYIDLSGKRLLEFTLINE--EMLT	209
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	IPRFDIPRSYLFIDIECHFDK-KFPSVFNPNISHTSYCYIDLSGKRLLEFTLINE--EMLT	209
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	IPRFDIPRSYLFIDIECHFDK-KFPSVFNPNISHTSYCYIDLSGKRLLEFTLINE--EMLT	209
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	IPRFDIPRSYLFIDIECHFDK-KFPSVFNPNISHTSYCYIDLSGKRLLEFTLINE--EMLT	209
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	----MAPFRILSHDIECAGRKGHFPEPTHDPVIQIAN-LTLQGEAQPFV-----	373
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	----MAPFRILSHDIECAGRKGHFPEPTHDPVIQIAN-LTLQGEAQPFV-----	353
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	----MAPFRILSHDIECAGRKGHFPEPTHDPVIQIAN-LVTHQGEDQPFV-----	353
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	----MAPFRILSHDIECAGRKGHFPEPTHDPVIQIAN-LVTLQGEQPFV-----	355
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	----MAPFRILSHDIECAGRKGHFPEAKHDPVIQIAN-LVTLQGEDHDPFV-----	347
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	----MAPFRILSHDIECAGRKGHFPEAKHDPVIQIAN-LVTLQGEDQPFV-----	342
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	----IAPQVRLSHDIECAGRKGVFPEPDKDPVIQIAN-MVLRQGEKDPFI-----	355
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	----IAPLRLVSHDIECAGRKGIFPEPERDPVIQICS-LGLRWGEPEPFL-----	347
sp P52431 DPOD1_MOUSE	----IAPLRLVSHDIECAGRKGIFPEPERDPVIQICS-LGLRWGEPEPFL-----	349
sp P28340 DPOD1_HUMAN	----IAPLRLVSHDIECAGRKGIFPEPERDPVIQICS-LGLRWGEPEPFL-----	351
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	----IAPLRLVSHDIECAGRKGIFPEPERDPVIQICS-LGLRWGEPEPFL-----	351
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	----IAPLRLVSHDIECAGRKGIFPEPERDPVIQICS-LGLRWGEPEPFL-----	351
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	----IAPLRLVSHDIECAGRKGIFPEPERDPVIQICS-LGLRWGEPEPFL-----	351
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	----IAPLRLVSHDIECAGRKGIFPEPERDPVIQICS-LGLRWGEPEPFL-----	350

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	GWNVVCFLRLVQKHAERYR---IPL---RLGRDNTELEWREHGFKNG---VF-----	265
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	GWNVVCFLRLMLQKHAERYR---IPL---RFGDRSSELEWREHGFKNG---VF-----	265
tr A0A5Y2S1M3 A0A5Y2S1M3_SALER	GWNVVCFLRLMLQKHAERYR---IPL---RLGRDNSELEWREHGFKNG---VF-----	265
tr A0A2B7LUW5 A0A2B7LUW5_9ESCH	GWNVVCFLRLMLQKHAERYR---IPL---RLGRDNSELEWREHGFKNG---VF-----	265
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	GWNVVCFLRLMLQKHAERYR---IPL---RLGRDNSELEWREHGFKNG---VF-----	265
tr A0A6N3R803 A0A6N3R803_SHIFL	GWNVVCFLRLMLQKHAERYR---LPL---RLGRDNSELEWREHGFKNG---VF-----	265
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	GWNVVCFLRLMLQKHAERYR---LPL---RLGRDNSELEWREHGFKNG---VF-----	265
tr A0A3P6LPK6 A0A3P6LPK6_SHIDY	GWNVVCFLRLMLQKHAERYR---LPL---RLGRDNSELEWREHGFKNG---VF-----	265
tr A0A0K0QSA0 A0A0K0QSA0_9CAUD	GWNSNRFDIAYIITRYLNIFGQNVVRHFSFPGKVTAKTTTQYQ--NE-----QL-----	253
tr A0A1W5POA4 A0A1W5POA4_9CAUD	GWNSNRFDIAYIITRYLNIFGQNVVRHFSFPGKVTAKTTTQYQ--NE-----QL-----	253
tr A0A7U3VGB5 A0A7U3VGB5_9CAUD	GWNVEGFDIPIYVNRKINVLGVSGMRLSFPFGKITSKVITNMYG--DK-----EI-----	260
tr A0A5Q2F6H2 A0A5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	GWNIEGFDIPIYIMNRVKQILGERTMKRFSPLNKVSSKIITNMYG--DK-----EI-----	259
tr A0A2K9VME2 A0A2K9VME2_9CAUD	GWNIEGFDIPIYIMNRVKMLGERSMKRFSPIGRVSKSLIQNMYG--SK-----EI-----	308
tr A0A249XWD5 A0A249XWD5_9CAUD	GWNIEGFDIPIYIMNRVKMLGERSMKRFSPIGRVSKSLIQNMYG--SK-----EI-----	259
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	GWNIEGFDIPIYIMNRVKMLGERSMKRFSPIGRVSKSLIQNMYG--SK-----EI-----	259
tr A0A2U7NJH8 A0A2U7NJH8_9CAUD	GWNIEGFDIPIYIQRINVLGRSTALRMSPIGSRVTKLVTTQYQ--EE-----RL-----	258
tr A0A0B5A2H2 A0A0B5A2H2_9CAUD	GWNVEGFDNPMYVNRKINVLGENTAKRSLFNKRVNKSIIQNIYQ--DK-----EV-----	259
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	GWNVEGFDIPIYVNRKINIFGESTAKRSLFHRKTRVKVIENMYG--SR-----EI-----	262
tr A0A1Z1LY62 A0A1Z1LY62_9CAUD	GWNTEGFDIPIYVNRKINIFGESTAKRSLFHRKTRVKVIENMYG--ER-----EV-----	261
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	TFNGHNFDIRYVSNRLQLLQSSVCFR-LPDQREPVKLVYERSLASHRAGGMANTTFH	314
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	TFNGHNFDIRYVSNRLQLLQSSVCFR-LPDQREPVKLVYERSLASHRAGGMANTTFH	319
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	TFNGHNFDIRYVSNRLQLLQSSVCFR-LPDQREPVKLVYERSLASHRAGGMANTTFH	319
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	TFNGHNFDIRYVSNRLQLLQSSVCFR-LPDQREPVKLVYERSLASHRAGGMANTTFH	319
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	TFNGHNFDIRYVSNRLQLLQSSVCFR-LPDQREPVKLVYERSLASHRAGGMANTTFH	319
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	TFNGHNFDIRYVSNRLQLLQSSVCFR-LPDQREPVKLVYERSLASHRAGGMANTTFH	319
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	GYNICKFDLPYLIERAEVLKIVEFPFL-GRIR--NSRVVRDRTTFNSR---QYGMRESK	469
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	GYNICKFDLPYLIERAEVLKIVEFPFL-GRIR--NSRVVRDRTTFNSR---QYGMRESK	449
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	GYNICKFDLPYLIERAEVLKIVEFPFL-GRIR--NSRVVRDRTTFNSR---QYGMRESK	449
sp Q9LRE6 DPOD1_ORYSJ	GYNICKFDLPYLIERAEVLKIVEFPFL-GRIR--NSRVVRDRTTFNSR---QYGMRESK	451
sp Q9LVN7 DPOD1_ARATH	GYNICKFDLPYLIERAEVLKIVEFPFL-GRVK--NSRVVRDRTTFSSR---QYGMRESK	443
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	GYNICKFDLPYLIERAEVLKIVEFPFL-GRVK--NSRVVRDRTTFSSR---QYGMRESK	438
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	GYNIQNFDLPYLINRAQTLKVFPPFL-GRIR--SLKSVIRDSSSFQSK---QMGRENK	451
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	GYNIQNFDLPYLISRAQTLKVFPPFL-GRVT--GLRSNIRDSSSFQSK---QVGRRDSK	443
sp P52431 DPOD1_MOUSE	GYNIQNFDLPYLISRAQTLKVFPPFL-GRVT--GLRSNIRDSSSFQSK---QVGRRDSK	445
sp P28340 DPOD1_HUMAN	GYNIQNFDLPYLISRAQTLKVFPPFL-GRVA--GLCSNIRDSSSFQSK---QTGRRDTK	447
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	GYNIQNFDLPYLISRAQTLKVFPPFL-GRVS--GLRSNIRDSSSFQSK---QTGRRDTK	447
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	GYNIQNFDLPYLISRAQTLKVFPPFL-GRVS--GLRSTIRDSSSFQSK---QTGRRDSK	447
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	GYNIQNFDLPYLISRAQTLKVFPPFL-GRVS--GLRSNIRDSSSFQSK---QTGRRDSK	447
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	GYNIQNFDLPYLISRAQTLKVFPPFL-GRVI--GLRSNIRDSSSFQSK---QTGRRDSK	446

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	----MDEIDRR-FAEDKPALATNLKDC	CELVLTQIFHKTEIMPFLLERATVNGLPADRHGG	368
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	----MDEIDRR-FAEDKPALATNLKDC	CELVTKIFHKTEIMPFLLERATVNGLPVDRHGG	368
tr AOA5Y2S1M3 AOA5Y2S1M3_SALER	----MDEIDRR-FAQDKPALATNLKDC	CELVTRIIFHKTEIMPFLLERATVNGLPVDRHGG	368
tr AOA2B7LUW5 AOA2B7LUW5_9ESCH	----MDEIDRR-FTEDKPALATNLKDC	CELVTFIFHKTEIMPFLLERATVNGLPVDRHGG	368
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	----MDEIDRR-FAEDKPALATNLKDC	CELVTFIFHKTEIMPFLLERATVNGLPVDRHGG	368
tr AOA6N3R803 AOA6N3R803_SHIFL	----MDEIDRR-FAEDKPALATNLKDC	CELVTFIFHKTEIMPFLLERATVNGLPVDRHGG	368
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	----MDEIDRR-FAEDKPALATNLKDC	CELVTFIFHKTEIMPFLLERATVNGLPVDRHGG	368
tr AOA3P6LPK6 AOA3P6LPK6_SHIDY	----MDEIDRR-FAEDKPALATNLKDC	CELVTFIFHKTEIMPFLLERATVNGLPVDRHGG	368
tr AOA0K0QSA0 AOA0K0QSA0_9CAUD	----LRQ-----KDHQTYITINIVD	VIRVLDIDGKRNFIELVLSVAYYAKINFPQVMS	352
tr AOA1W5POA4 AOA1W5POA4_9CAUD	----LRQ-----ADHQYITINIVD	VIRVLDIDGKRNFIELVLSVAYYAKINFPQVMS	352
tr AOA7U3VGB5 AOA7U3VGB5_9CAUD	----LRG-----SNHQYISYNIID	VYCVQAIIDAKRGFINLSISMGGYARMNIATVMS	358
tr AOA5Q2F6H2 AOA5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	----LRE-----TNHQYISYNIID	VESVQAIIDAVRGFIDLAIMSYAKMPYQGVMS	357
tr AOA2K9VME2 AOA2K9VME2_9CAUD	----LRE-----TNHQYISYNIID	VESVQAIIDKIRGFDLVLMSYAKMFPQGVMS	406
tr AOA249XWD5 AOA249XWD5_9CAUD	----LRE-----TNHQYISYNIID	VESVQAIIDKIRGFDLVLMSYAKMFPQGVMS	357
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	----LRE-----TNHQYISYNIID	VESVQAIIDKIRGFDLVLMSYAKMFPQGVMS	357
tr AOA2U7NJH8 AOA2U7NJH8_9CAUD	----LRV-----NNHQYISYNIID	VERVQIDDKRNFITLSLSIAYYSKMQIQSVFS	357
tr AOA0B5A2H2 AOA0B5A2H2_9CAUD	----LRE-----LDHQYISYNIID	VARVQIIDQKRQFINLSMSLGGYAKMQIQSVFS	357
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	----LRE-----SNHQYISYNIID	VYRVLQIDAKRQFINLSLDMGYAKIQIQSVFS	360
tr AOA1Z1LY62 AOA1Z1LY62_9CAUD	----LRE-----TNHQYISYNIID	VERVQIDQKRQFINLSLDMGYAKMQIQSVFS	359
tr AOA1S7DLM5 AOA1S7DLM5_MCV2	DDVDLRELRYHSLAALAELEMERV	CMDDACLCKYLWYSYRVPKIDAAAAYLLPQCLAE	492
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	DDVNLSEMYSNYDLQTSLEMGKVC	IIDACLCKYLWYGGVEKTDAGASTYIILPQSMVFE	496
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	DDVDLAQMYKDYNLNIALDMARVC	IIDACLCKYLWYGGVEKTDAGASTYIILPQSMVFE	494
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VARV	DDVDLAQMYKDYNLNIALDMARVC	IIDACLCKYLWYGGVEKTDAGASTYIILPQSMVFE	494
sp AOA7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	DDIDLQMYKDYNLNIALDMARVC	IIDACLCKYLWYGGVEKTDAGASTYIILPQSMVFE	495
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	DDVDLAQMYKDYNLNIALDMARVC	IIDACLCKYLWYGGVEKTDAGASTYIILPQSMVFE	495
tr AOA287NEC0 AOA287NEC0_HORVV	-----NSETRRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PQRLLDKLMIYINYVEMARVTGVPISFLLS	570
tr AOA3B6JHK9 AOA3B6JHK9_WHEAT	-----NSETRRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PQRLLDKLMIYINYVEMARVTGVPISFLLS	550
tr AOA1D6QLT8 AOA1D6QLT8_MAIZE	-----NPETRRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PQRLLDKLMIYINYVEMARVTGVPISFLLS	550
sp Q9LRE6 DPD01_ORYSJ	-----NSETRRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PQRLLDKLMIYINYVEMARVTGVPISFLLS	552
sp Q9LVN7 DPD01_ARATH	-----NAETRRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PQRLLDKLMIYINYVEMARVTGVPISFLLS	544
tr AOA078I2E2 AOA078I2E2_BRANA	-----NAETRRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PQRLLDKLMCIYINYVEMARVTGVPISFLLS	539
tr DOVEW7 DOVEW7_XENLA	-----NDQTRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PLRLLERLMVAVINYMARVTGVPISYLLS	552
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	-----NEQTRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PLRLLERLMVAVINYMARVTGVPISYLLS	544
sp P52431 DPD01_MOUSE	-----NEQTRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PLRLLERLMVAVINYMARVTGVPISYLLS	546
sp P28340 DPD01_HUMAN	-----NDQTRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PLRLLERLMVAVINYMARVTGVPISYLLS	548
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	-----NEQTRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PLRLLERLMVAVINYMARVTGVPISYLLS	548
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	-----NDQTRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PLRLLERLMVAVINYMARVTGVPISYLLS	548
tr AOA5G2QET9 AOA5G2QET9_PIG	-----NDQTRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PLRLLERLMVAVINYMARVTGVPISYLLS	548
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	-----NDQTRRLAVYCLLDAYL	PLRLLERLMVAVINYMARVTGVPISYLLS	547

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	-----LY-DSVLVLDYKSLYPSI	IRTFLLIDPVGLVEGMA-----QP	445
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	-----LY-DSVLVLDYKSLYPSI	IRTFLLIDPVGLVEGMA-----HP	445
tr AOA5Y2S1M3 AOA5Y2S1M3_SALER	-----LY-DSVLVLDYKSLYPSI	IRTFLLIDPVGLVEGMA-----QP	445
tr AOA2B7LUW5 AOA2B7LUW5_9ESCH	-----LY-DSVLVLDYKSLYPSI	IRTFLLIDPVGLVEGMA-----QP	445
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	-----LY-DSVLVLDYKSLYPSI	IRTYLIDPVGLVEGMA-----QP	445
tr AOA6N3R803 AOA6N3R803_SHIFL	-----LY-DSVLVLDYKSLYPSI	IRTFLLIDPVGLVEGMA-----QP	445
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	-----LY-DSVLVLDYKSLYPSI	IRTFLLIDPVGLVEGMA-----QP	445
tr AOA3P6LPK6 AOA3P6LPK6_SHIDY	-----LY-DSVLVLDYKSLYPSI	IRTFLLIDPVGLVEGMA-----QP	445
tr AOA0K0QSA0 AOA0K0QSA0_9CAUD	-----PY-KYIVSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIANSFAVRPL-DEYINKT----	AP 440
tr AOA1W5POA4 AOA1W5POA4_9CAUD	-----PY-RYIVSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIANSFAVRPM-HEYINKT----	AP 440
tr AOA7U3VGB5 AOA7U3VGB5_9CAUD	-----AY-KYVMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIAGQFAPPKL-ADFINKI----	AP 446
tr AOA5Q2F6H2 AOA5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	-----AY-RYIMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIVGQFKLHPL-GEYINKT----	AP 445
tr AOA2K9VME2 AOA2K9VME2_9CAUD	-----AR-RYIMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIRGQFKVHPI-HEYIAGT----	AP 494
tr AOA249XWD5 AOA249XWD5_9CAUD	-----AR-RYIMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIRGQFKVHPI-HEYIAGT----	AP 445
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	-----AR-RYIMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIRGQFKVHPI-HEYIAGT----	AP 445
tr AOA2U7NJH8 AOA2U7NJH8_9CAUD	-----AY-KYVMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPDTLVGSFAVHPI-LDYVNVK----	AP 445
tr AOA0B5A2H2 AOA0B5A2H2_9CAUD	-----AY-KYIMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIAGQFKLHPI-AEYINMT----	AP 445
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	-----HY-KYVMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETIAGTFKVAPL-HDYINAV----	AE 448
tr AOA1Z1LY62 AOA1Z1LY62_9CAUD	-----SY-KYVMSFDLTSYPSI	IRQVNI SPETLAGQFQLHPI-HDYINKV----	AP 447
tr AOA1S7DLM5 AOA1S7DLM5_MCV2	-----LFDTNVMVHDYNSLYPNV	ICFIGNLSPETLVGVVANAHRLDAELNMQELRRRF	589
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	-----MFSNNVLIIFDYNLSLYPNV	ICFIGNLSPETLVGVVFNNTLEAEINKNISKMYP	593
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	-----MFSNNVLIIFDYNLSLYPNV	ICFIGNLSPETLVGVVFNNTLEAEINKNILLQKYP	591
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VARV	-----MFSNNVLIIFDYNLSLYPNV	ICFIGNLSPETLVGVVFNNTLEAEINKNILLQKYP	591
sp AOA7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	-----MFSNNVLIIFDYNLSLYPNV	ICFIGNLSPETLVGVVFNNTLEAEINKNILLQKYP	592
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	-----MFSNNVLIIFDYNLSLYPNV	ICFIGNLSPETLVGVVFNNTLEAEINKNILLQKYP	592
tr AOA287NEC0 AOA287NEC0_HORVV	-----FYEKPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVLPVPEVDRK-----LNLP	657
tr AOA3B6JHK9 AOA3B6JHK9_WHEAT	-----FYEKPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVLPVPEVDRK-----LNLP	637
tr AOA1D6QLT8 AOA1D6QLT8_MAIZE	-----FYEKPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAYNLCTVLPVPEEARK-----LNLP	637
sp Q9LRE6 DPD01_ORYSJ	-----FYEKPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAYNLCTVLPVPEEARK-----LNLP	639
sp Q9LVN7 DPD01_ARATH	-----FYEKPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAYNLCTVLPVPEVDRK-----LNLP	631
tr AOA078I2E2 AOA078I2E2_BRANA	-----FYEKPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAYNLCTVLPVPEVDRK-----LNLP	626
tr DOVEW7 DOVEW7_XENLA	-----YYDVPPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVTLRPGAAQK-----LGLK	629
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	-----YYDVPPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVTLRPGAAQK-----LGLK	629
sp P52431 DPD01_MOUSE	-----YYDVPPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVTLRPGAAQK-----LGLT	631
sp P28340 DPD01_HUMAN	-----YYDVPPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVTLRPGAAQK-----LGLT	633
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	-----YYDVPPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVTLRPGAAQK-----LGLT	633
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	-----YYDVPPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVTLRPGAAQK-----LGLT	633
tr AOA5G2QET9 AOA5G2QET9_PIG	TPPRTARYYDVPITIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVTLRPGAAQK-----LGLT	653
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	-----YYDVPPIATIDFASLYPSI	IMMAHNLCTVTLRPGAAQK-----LGLT	632

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	-----HGNKPLSQA	491
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	-----QGNKPLSQA	491
tr A0A5Y2S1M3 A0A5Y2S1M3_SALER	-----QGNKPLSQA	491
tr A0A2B7LUW5 A0A2B7LUW5_9ESCH	-----QGNKPLSQA	491
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	-----QGNKPLSQA	491
tr A0A6N3R803 A0A6N3R803_SHIFL	-----QGNKPLSQA	491
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	-----QGNKPLSQA	491
tr A0A3P6LPK6 A0A3P6LPK6_SHIDY	-----QGNKPLSQA	491
tr A0A0K0QSA0 A0A0K0QSA0_9CAUD	HELEHLTDAHNQIMDPDFDFYSDFSDSKAVLTKTLTKQMLKAVKKVCEKKAIAQANTAQLN	552
tr A0A1W5P0A4 A0A1W5P0A4_9CAUD	HELEHLTDAHNQMINPDEFYEDFGDES KAVLTKLSKQMLKAVKKVCEKKAIAQANTAQLN	552
tr A0A7U3VGB5 A0A7U3VGB5_9CAUD	KLIKSIIN-P-IFGDYMNLDLFSRDFTESEIEYKLSLSQEELNALETQCENYITLCDTNOIN	556
tr A0A5Q2F6H2 A0A5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	KVLNDKFKG-TIDKFTVNVVYEDFSDDMKAEILTYTEECLEKLMFECKHAEILGNTNOLN	556
tr A0A2K9VME2 A0A2K9VME2_9CAUD	KIIMK-GAG-SCSTKPEVERYVKFSDDFLNELSNYTESVLNSLIEECEKAATLANTNOLN	604
tr A0A249XWD5 A0A249XWD5_9CAUD	KIIMK-GAG-SCSTKPEVERYVKFSDDFLNELSNYTESVLNSLIEECEKAATLANTNOLN	555
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	KIIMK-GAG-SCSTKPEVERYVKFSDDFLNELSNYTESVLNSLIEECEKAATLANTNOLN	555
tr A0A2U7NJH8 A0A2U7NJH8_9CAUD	RAMQENTNT-DYGMNKVLDNFVDFNEETLELLNLLSISELQQLEKAAKKNVTVCDDTNOIN	556
tr A0A0B5A2H2 A0A0B5A2H2_9CAUD	DILNHKTFG-NKSLKTDINHRAFDDEVKEMKELTEGDLMSMLLDDKADRAAIASNTAON	556
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	EALHNPNSL-VDE-PLDVDYRFDFSDIEKEIKKLSAKSLNEMLFRAQRTEVAGMTAON	558
tr A0A1Z1LY62 A0A1Z1LY62_9CAUD	EALHHDFTFG-SGG-VPDVDVRNDFDDETKALLSTMSKALKQFLDKCDRASIAGNTAON	557
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	-----RTLYDSMOYT	656
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	-----KAIYDSMOYT	660
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	-----KAIYDSMOYT	658
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	-----KAIYDSMOYT	658
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	-----KAIYDSMOYT	658
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	-----KAIYDSMOYT	659
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	-----RAVLDRGROLA	716
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	-----RAVLDRGROLA	696
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	-----RAVLDRGROLA	696
sp Q9LRE6 DPO1_ORYSJ	-----RAVLDRGROLA	698
sp Q9LVN7 DPO1_ARATH	-----KAVLDGROLA	690
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	-----KAVLDGROLA	685
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	-----QKVLDRGROLA	696
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	-----RQVLDRGROLA	688
sp P52431 DPO1_MOUSE	-----RQVLDRGROLA	690
sp P28340 DPO1_HUMAN	-----RQVLDRGROLA	692
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	-----RQVLDRGROLA	692
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	-----RQVLDRGROLA	692
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	-----RQVLDRGROLA	712
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	-----RQVLDRGROLA	691

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	LKILMNAFYGLVLTACRFFDPRLASSITMRGHAIMRQTKALI-----	534
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	LKILMNAFYGLVLTACRFFDPRLASSITMRGHAIMRQTKALI-----	534
tr A0A5Y2S1M3 A0A5Y2S1M3_SALER	LKILMNAFYGLVLTACRFFDPRLASSITMRGHAIMRQTKALI-----	534
tr A0A2B7LUW5 A0A2B7LUW5_9ESCH	LKILMNAFYGLVLTACRFFDPRLASSITMRGHQIMRQTKALI-----	534
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	LKILMNAFYGLVLTACRFFDPRLASSITMRGHQIMRQTKALI-----	534
tr A0A6N3R803 A0A6N3R803_SHIFL	LKILMNAFYGLVLTACRFFDPRLASSITMRGHQIMRQTKALI-----	534
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	LKILMNAFYGLVLTACRFFDPRLASSITMRGHQIMRQTKALI-----	534
tr A0A3P6LPK6 A0A3P6LPK6_SHIDY	LKILMNAFYGLVLTACRFFDPRLASSITMRGHQIMRQTKALI-----	534
tr A0A0K0QSA0 A0A0K0QSA0_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNEHFYFRYDLRNASAITMFGQLAIQWIERKVNE-----	597
tr A0A1W5P0A4 A0A1W5P0A4_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNEHFYFRYDLRNASAITMFGQLAIQWIERKVNE-----	597
tr A0A7U3VGB5 A0A7U3VGB5_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNIYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQMAIQWIERKVNE-----	601
tr A0A5Q2F6H2 A0A5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNIYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQMAIQWIERKVNE-----	601
tr A0A2K9VME2 A0A2K9VME2_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNIHFYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQVGIQWIARKINE-----	649
tr A0A249XWD5 A0A249XWD5_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNIHFYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQVGIQWIARKINE-----	600
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	RKILINSLYGALGNIHFYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQVGIQWIARKINE-----	600
tr A0A2U7NJH8 A0A2U7NJH8_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNIHFYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQCAIQWIERKVNE-----	601
tr A0A0B5A2H2 A0A0B5A2H2_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNIYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQMAIQWIERKVNE-----	601
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	RKILINSLYGALGNIHFYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQMAIQWIERKVNE-----	603
tr A0A1Z1LY62 A0A1Z1LY62_9CAUD	RKILINSLYGALGNIHFYFRYDLRNASAITLFGQMAIQWIERKVNE-----	602
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	YKIVANSVYGLMGFYNSLYSYSAKCTTIGRVMITYLDRVVDGATLCAGVLRASEPR	716
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	YKIVANSVYGLMGFRNSVLYSYSAKCTTAIGRMMILYLSVLDGSKINSKFTFAKLPL	720
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	YKIVANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSAKCTSIGRMMILYLSVLDGSKINSKFTFAKLPL	718
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	YKIVANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSAKCTSIGRMMILYLSVLDGSKINSKFTFAKLPL	718
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	YKIVANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSAKCTSIGRMMILYLSVLDGSKINSKFTFAKLPL	719
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	YKIVANSVYGLMGFRNSALYSYSAKCTSIGRMMILYLSVLDGSKINSKFTFAKLPL	719
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	761
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	741
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	741
sp Q9LRE6 DPO1_ORYSJ	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	743
sp Q9LVN7 DPO1_ARATH	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	735
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	730
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	741
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	733
sp P52431 DPO1_MOUSE	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	735
sp P28340 DPO1_HUMAN	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	737
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	737
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	737
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	757
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	LKIVANSVYGFGTATVQGLPCLEISSVTSYGRQMIHTKKLVED-----	736

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	-----EA-QGYDVIYGDTS	TFVWLKGAHSEDEAARIG-RELV	570
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	-----EA-QGYDVIYGDTS	TFVWLKRARSEEEAAQIG-RSLV	570
tr AOA5Y2S1M3 AOA5Y2S1M3_SALER	-----EA-QGYDVIYGDTS	TFVWLRRARHSEADAAKIG-HMLV	570
tr AOA2B7LUW5 AOA2B7LUW5_9ESCH	-----EA-QGYDVIYGDTS	TFVWLKGAHCEEEAAKIG-RALV	570
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	-----EA-QGYDVIYGDTS	TFVWLKGAHSEEEAAKIG-RALV	570
tr AOA6N3R803 AOA6N3R803_SHIFL	-----EA-QGYDVIYGDTS	TFVWLKGAHSEEEAAKIG-RALV	570
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	-----EA-QGYDVIYGDTS	TFVWLKGAHSEEEAAKIG-RALV	570
tr AOA3P6LPK6 AOA3P6LPK6_SHIDY	-----EA-QGYDVIYGDTS	TFVWLKGAHSEEEAAKIG-RALV	570
tr AOA0K0QSA0 AOA0K0QSA0_9CAUD	-----YLNQLCNTTDYAYVRVC	ITDSTIYVCMNDVIEK----VGGESKF	636
tr AOA1W5POA4 AOA1W5POA4_9CAUD	-----YLNELCNTTDYAYVRVC	ITDSTIYVCMNDVIAK----VGGESKF	636
tr AOA7U3VGB5 AOA7U3VGB5_9CAUD	-----YLNELCGTTHDPYVVI	ITDSTIYIELSPLIEK----VG-IDKF	639
tr AOA5Q2F6H2 AOA5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	-----YLNKVCGTGEGHSFVVA	ITDSTIYVCDVKVIEK----VG-LERF	639
tr AOA2K9VME2 AOA2K9VME2_9CAUD	-----YLNKVCGTNGEDFIAAG	DTDSVYVCDVKVIEK----VG-LDRF	687
tr AOA249XWD5 AOA249XWD5_9CAUD	-----YLNKVCGTNGEDFIAAG	DTDSVYVCDVKVIEK----VG-LDRF	638
sp P04415 DPOL_BP14	-----YLNKVCGTNDEDFIAAG	DTDSVYVCDVKVIEK----VG-LDRF	638
tr AOA2U7NJH8 AOA2U7NJH8_9CAUD	-----YLNQVGVGTNNHKYVVI	YGDTSVYICIDPLVKNK----VG-EHKF	639
tr AOA0B5A2H2 AOA0B5A2H2_9CAUD	-----YLNKTIGTNNFNFYVIA	GDTSVYVYCADKIEK----VG-EDKF	639
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	-----YLNKVCGTGEGEAFVLI	YGDTSIYVSADKIIDK----VG-ESKF	641
tr AOA1Z1LY62 AOA1Z1LY62_9CAUD	-----YMNKVVGLDHHKFFVIA	GDTSVYICVDKLIDK----VG-EDKF	640
tr AOA1S7DLM5 AOA1S7DLM5_MCV2	NPLLASAPPRARDVDVSAAL	GHELELRFRSVYGDTSIFLELNL	EVQTTLVA-----
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	NPFEDGRVY--TLNDDTGV	DKHYNFVKTVYGDTSVFLEMNTQ	-DVDTSIIIA-----
sp F0D005 DPOL_VAR67	NPFYMDRDI--NPIVKTSLP	IDYRFRFRSVYGDTSVFTEIDSQ	-DVKISIEIA-----
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	NPFYMDRDI--NPIVKTSLP	IDYRFRFRSVYGDTSVFTEIDSQ	-DVKISIEIA-----
sp AOA7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	NPFYMDRDI--NPIVKTSLP	IDYRFRFRSVYGDTSVFTEIDSQ	-DVKISIEIA-----
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	NPFYMDRDI--NPIVKTSLP	IDYRFRFRSVYGDTSVFTEIDSQ	-DVKISIEIA-----
tr AOA287NEC0 AOA287NEC0_HORVV	-----KFTTVGGYEHNAEVVI	YGDTSVMVQFGVS-TVKDAMKLG	-----
tr AOA3B6JHK9 AOA3B6JHK9_WHEAT	-----KFTTLGGYEHNAEVVI	YGDTSVMVQFGAS-TVEDAMKLG	-----
tr AOA1D6QLT8 AOA1D6QLT8_MAIZE	-----KFTTVGGYEHTAEVVI	YGDTSVMVQFGVS-TVEDAMKLG	-----
sp Q9LRE6 DPD1_ORYSJ	-----KFTTLGGYEHNAEVVI	YGDTSVMVQFGVS-TVEDAMKLG	-----
sp Q9LVN7 DPD1_ARATH	-----KFTTLGGYQYNAEVVI	YGDTSVMVQFGVS-DVEAAMTLG	-----
tr AOA078I2E2 AOA078I2E2_BRANA	-----KFTTLGGYEYNAEVVI	YGDTSVMVQFGVP-DVEAAMTLG	-----
tr DOVEW7 DOVEW7_XENLA	-----KYTLDNQYKADAKVVI	YGDTSVMCKLGQV-TVAEAMELG	-----
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	-----KYTLENGYDANAKVVI	YGDTSVMCRFGVS-SVAEAMSLG	-----
sp P52431 DPD1_MOUSE	-----KYTVENGYDANAKVVI	YGDTSVMCRFGVS-SVAEAMSLG	-----
sp P28340 DPD1_HUMAN	-----KYTVENGYSTSAKVVI	YGDTSVMCRFGVS-SVAEAMALG	-----
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	-----KYTTENGYSAKVVVI	YGDTSVMCRFGVS-SVAEAMALG	-----
tr M3VUU4 M3VUU4_FELCA	-----KYTVENGYSTSAKVVI	YGDTSVMCRFGVS-SVAEAMALG	-----
tr AOA5G2QET9 AOA5G2QET9_PIG	-----KYTVENGYSTSAKVVI	YGDTSVMCRFGVS-SVAEAMALG	-----
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	-----KYTVENGYSTSAKVVI	YGDTSVMCRFGVS-SVAEAMALG	-----

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	YQEYVRETIDNLTGKLDQ-L	VYRKLRRPLSEYQRNVPPHV	-----RA---	705
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	YQDYVRETIDKLMAGELDDR	-LVYRKLRRPLSEYQRNVPPHV	-----RA---	705
tr AOA5Y2S1M3 AOA5Y2S1M3_SALER	YQDYVRETIDKLMAGELDAQ	-LVYRKLRRPLHEYQRNVPPHV	-----RA---	705
tr AOA2B7LUW5 AOA2B7LUW5_9ESCH	YQEYVRETIDKLMAGELDAR	-LVYRKLRRPLSEYQRNVPPHV	-----RA---	705
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	YQEYVRETIDKLMAGELDAR	-LVYRKLRRPLSEYQRNVPPHV	-----RA---	705
tr AOA6N3R803 AOA6N3R803_SHIFL	YQEYVRETIDKLMAGELDAR	-LVYRKLRRPLSEYQRNVPPHV	-----RA---	705
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	YQEYVRETIDKLMAGELDAR	-LVYRKLRRPLSEYQRNVPPHV	-----RA---	705
tr AOA3P6LPK6 AOA3P6LPK6_SHIDY	YQEYVRETIDKLMAGELDAR	-LVYRKLRRPLSEYQRNVPPHV	-----RA---	705
tr AOA0K0QSA0 AOA0K0QSA0_9CAUD	LHESFKV-----	FEEYKALDYREIAGV-----	SS---	779
tr AOA1W5POA4 AOA1W5POA4_9CAUD	LHEHFKV-----	FEEYKALDYREIAGV-----	SS---	779
tr AOA7U3VGB5 AOA7U3VGB5_9CAUD	LQEYFKK-----	FENEFRLDYKVIAGV-----	RS---	782
tr AOA5Q2F6H2 AOA5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	LQYYYKQ-----	FESEYRELDYKVAEV-----	KT---	782
tr AOA2K9VME2 AOA2K9VME2_9CAUD	VQEYYKN-----	FEKEYRQLDYKVAEV-----	KT---	830
tr AOA249XWD5 AOA249XWD5_9CAUD	VQEYYKN-----	FEKEYRQLDYKVAEV-----	KT---	781
sp P04415 DPOL_BP14	VQEYYKN-----	FEKEYRQLDYKVAEV-----	KT---	781
tr AOA2U7NJH8 AOA2U7NJH8_9CAUD	LQEHFKS-----	FEKEFRELEYKSISAV-----	SS---	782
tr AOA0B5A2H2 AOA0B5A2H2_9CAUD	LQEYYKE-----	FESEFRQDYTTIASV-----	SS---	782
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	LQEYFKE-----	FEKEFRQLNYISIASV-----	SS---	784
tr AOA1Z1LY62 AOA1Z1LY62_9CAUD	LQTYFKE-----	FEHEFRQDYKTTAAV-----	SS---	783
tr AOA1S7DLM5 AOA1S7DLM5_MCV2	-----LLAEARLSSRQVCLE	MLRSLLEVDFAEFAARAQPLEMFL	LSRTHHRYNKAPDN	904
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	-----MLSNCSMTSIQVCVD	VLSKLSLEDFVRSAPLDMFL	LSRTHHCNYKSHDN	906
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	-----MLSEGRMNSNQVCID	ILRSLETDLRSEFDSRS	SPLFLFMLSRMHHLNYSADN	904
sp F0D006 DPOL_VARV	-----MLSEGRMNSNQVCID	ILRSLETDLRSEFDSRS	SPLFLFMLSRMHHLNYSADN	904
sp AOA7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	-----MLSEGRMNSNQVCID	ILRSLETDLRSEFDSRS	SPLFLFMLSRMHHLNYSADN	905
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	-----MLSEGRMNSNQVCID	ILRSLETDLRSEFDSRS	SPLFLFMLSRMHHLNYSADN	905
tr AOA287NEC0 AOA287NEC0_HORVV	AVQYVKNITSDLLMNRVDSL	LLVITKGLTKTGEDYAVKAAHVEL	--AERMRKRDA-----	935
tr AOA3B6JHK9 AOA3B6JHK9_WHEAT	AVQYVKNITSDLLMNRVDSL	LLVITKGLTKTGEDYAVKAAHVEL	--AERMRKRDA-----	915
tr AOA1D6QLT8 AOA1D6QLT8_MAIZE	AVQYVKNITSDLLMNRVDSL	LLVITKGLTKTGEDYAVKAAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	915
sp Q9LRE6 DPD1_ORYSJ	AVQYVKNITSDLLMNRVDSL	LLVITKGLTKTGEDYAVKAAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	917
sp Q9LVN7 DPD1_ARATH	AAENVKKTISDLLMNRIDSL	LLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKSAHGEL	--AERMRKRDA-----	909
tr AOA078I2E2 AOA078I2E2_BRANA	AAEYVKNITADLLMNRIDSL	LLVITKGLTKTGDDYEVKSAHGEL	--AERMRKRDA-----	904
tr DOVEW7 DOVEW7_XENLA	AVEHAKDVISDLLCNRIDIS	QLVITKELTRTAADEYAGQAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	916
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	AVAHAKDVISDLLCNRIDIS	QLVITKELTRAAADYAGQAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	908
sp P52431 DPD1_MOUSE	AVAHAKDVISDLLCNRIDIS	QLVITKELTRAAADYAGQAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	910
sp P28340 DPD1_HUMAN	AVAHAQDVISDLLCNRIDIS	QLVITKELTRAAADYAGQAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	912
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	AVAHAQDVISDLLCNRIDIS	QLVITKELTRAAADYAGQAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	912
tr M3VUU4 M3VUU4_FELCA	AVAHAQDVISDLLCNRIDIS	QLVITKELTRAAADYAGQAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	912
tr AOA5G2QET9 AOA5G2QET9_PIG	AVAHAQDVISDLLCNRIDIS	QLVITKELTRAAADYAGQAHVEL	--AERMRKRDP-----	932

tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	AVAHAQDVISDLLCNRIDISQVLITKELTRAAADYAGKQAHVEL--AERMRKRD-----	911
tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	--ARLADEQ-----NIKLRGPAQYQNRGTIKYVWTTNGP-----	737
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	--ARLADEE-----NLKRGRPAQYQNRGTIQYLWTVNGP-----	737
tr A0A5Y2S1M3 A0A5Y2S1M3_SALER	--ARLADEQ-----NLKRGRPAQYQNRGAIKYVWTVNGP-----	737
tr A0A2B7LUW5 A0A2B7LUW5_9ESCH	--ARLADEE-----NQKRGRPLQYQNRGTIKYVWTTNGP-----	737
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	--ARLADEE-----NQKRGRPLQYQNRGTIKYVWTTNGP-----	737
tr A0A6N3R803 A0A6N3R803_SHIFL	--ARLADEE-----NQKRGRPLQYQNRGTIKYVWTTNGP-----	737
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	--ARLADEE-----NQKRGRPLQYQNRGTIKYVWTTNGP-----	737
tr A0A3P6LPK6 A0A3P6LPK6_SHIDY	--ARLADEE-----NQKRGRPLQYQNRGTIKYVWTTNGP-----	737
tr A0A0K0QSA0 A0A0K0QSA0_9CAUD	--ANNITKYNDG---TGHPKIGTPNHIKGVLFNRLTRGI--QGITQIMEGEKVMVLPRLR	832
tr A0A1W5POA4 A0A1W5POA4_9CAUD	--ANNISKYNDG---AGFPKIGTPNHIKGVLFNRLTRGI--QGITPIMEGEKVMVLPRLR	832
tr A0A7U3VGB5 A0A7U3VGB5_9CAUD	--ANNIAKYDV---NGFPGKCPFHVRGVLTYRRAIKKY--DNLDPDISEGEKVMVLPK	834
tr A0A5Q2F6H2 A0A5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	--ANNIGKYDDG---AGYPDKGTPYHVKGALAYNRATAGF--EGITPIMEGEKVMVLPRLR	835
tr A0A2K9VME2 A0A2K9VME2_9CAUD	--ANDIAKYDD---KGWPGFKCFFHIRGVLTYRRAVSGL---GVAPILDGNKVMVLPRLR	881
tr A0A249XWD5 A0A249XWD5_9CAUD	--ANDIAKYDD---KGWPGFKCFFHIRGVLTYRRAVSGL---GVAPILDGNKVMVLPRLR	832
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	--ANDIAKYDD---KGWPGFKCFFHIRGVLTYRRAVSGL---GVAPILDGNKVMVLPRLR	832
tr A0A2U7NJH8 A0A2U7NJH8_9CAUD	--ANNIAKYDV---DGFPYKCPYHIRGILTYHRAINGT---YAPRIADGDKVMVLPRLR	833
tr A0A0B5A2H2 A0A0B5A2H2_9CAUD	--ANNIAKYDD---NGFPGKCPFHVRGVLTYRRAIKKY--DNLDPDISEGEKVMVLPK	834
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	--ANNIAKYDV---GGFPGKCPFHVRGVLTYRRAIKKY--DNLDPDISEGEKVMVLPK	836
tr A0A1Z1LY62 A0A1Z1LY62_9CAUD	--ANNIMKYDV---GGYPPGKCPYHIRGILTYRRAIKKY--DNLDPDISEGEKVMVLPK	835
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	PNVELVNRYN RENLEPIELGERYYFAYICASELPWQLAVANVRNHERIV--DASYVLP--	960
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	PNNMFLVNEYN NNAEIEIGERYFFAYICPSKYPWQKLVNIKTYETII--DRSFKLN--	962
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	PNNMYLVTEYN KNNPETIELGERYYFAYICANVPWTKKLVNIKTYETII--DRSFKLG--	960
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	PNNMYLVTEYN KNNPETIELGERYYFAYICANVPWTKKLVNIKTYETII--DRSFKLG--	960
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	PNNMYLVTEYN KNNPETIELGERYYFAYICANVPWTKKLVNIKTYETII--DRSFKLG--	961
sp Q57191 DPOL_VACCA	PNNMYLVTEYN KNNPETIELGERYYFAYICANVPWTKKLVNIKTYETII--DRSFKLG--	961
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	-----ATAPTVDGDRVPYVIKAA-----KGAKAYEKSE--DPIYVLD--	970
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	-----ATAPTVDGDRVPYVIKAA-----KGAKAYEKSE--DPIYVLD--	950
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	-----ATAPTVDGDRVPYVIKAA-----KGAKAYEKSE--DPIYVLD--	950
sp Q9LRE6 DPD01_ORYSJ	-----ATAPTVDGDRVPYVIKAA-----KGAKAYEKSE--DPIYVLD--	952
sp Q9LVN7 DPD01_ARATH	-----ATAPNVGDRVPYVIKAA-----KGAKAYEKSE--DPIYVLD--	944
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	-----ATAPNVGDRVPYVIKAA-----KGAKAYEKSE--DPIYVLD--	939
tr DOVEW7 DOVEW7_XENLA	-----GSAPNLGDRVPYVIIGAA-----KGVAAYMKSE--DPLFVLE--	951
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	-----GSAPNLGDRVPYVIIGAA-----KGVAAYMKSE--DPLFVLE--	943
sp P52431 DPD01_MOUSE	-----GSAPSLGDRVPYVIIGAA-----KGVAAYMKSE--DPLFVLE--	945
sp P28340 DPD01_HUMAN	-----GSAPSLGDRVPYVIIGAA-----KGVAAYMKSE--DPLFVLE--	947
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	-----GSAPSLGDRVPYVIIGAA-----KGVAAYMKSE--DPLFVLE--	947
tr M3VU04 M3VU04_FELCA	-----GSAPSLGDRVPYVIIGAA-----KGVAAYMKSE--DPLFVLE--	947
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	-----GSAPSLGDRVPYVIIGAA-----KGVAAYMKSE--DPLFVLE--	967
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	-----GSAPSLGDRVPYVIIGAA-----KGVAAYMKSE--DPLFVLE--	946

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	-----QPVAEGILPFIDNFA-----TLLTGQL-----	780
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	-----QPVAEGILPFIDNFA-----TLLTGQL-----	780
tr A0A5Y2S1M3 A0A5Y2S1M3_SALER	-----QPVAEGILPFIDNFA-----TLLTGQL-----	780
tr A0A2B7LUW5 A0A2B7LUW5_9ESCH	-----QPVAEGILPFIDNFA-----TLLTGQL-----	780
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	-----QPVAEGILPFIDNFA-----TLLTGQL-----	780
tr A0A6N3R803 A0A6N3R803_SHIFL	-----QPVAEGILPFIDNFA-----TLLTGQL-----	780
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	-----QPVAEGILPFIDNFA-----TLLTGQL-----	780
tr A0A3P6LPK6 A0A3P6LPK6_SHIDY	-----QPVAEGILPFIDNFA-----TLLTGQL-----	780
tr A0A0K0QSA0 A0A0K0QSA0_9CAUD	-----EKHVI-----SPLKNITEACKI-----DYEKR	890
tr A0A1W5POA4 A0A1W5POA4_9CAUD	-----EKHVI-----SPLQNIITEACKI-----DYEKR	890
tr A0A7U3VGB5 A0A7U3VGB5_9CAUD	-----GKTYK-----KPLEGMCESAGM-----DYEKR	892
tr A0A5Q2F6H2 A0A5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	-----QKSFV-----KPLTGMSEAGL-----DYEKR	893
tr A0A2K9VME2 A0A2K9VME2_9CAUD	-----QKSFV-----KPLAGMCEAGM-----DYEKR	939
tr A0A249XWD5 A0A249XWD5_9CAUD	-----QKSFV-----KPLAGMCEAGM-----DYEKR	890
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	-----QKSFV-----KPLAGMCEAGM-----DYEKR	890
tr A0A2U7NJH8 A0A2U7NJH8_9CAUD	-----EKTFF-----KPLAALTEACKI-----DYEKR	891
tr A0A0B5A2H2 A0A0B5A2H2_9CAUD	-----NKTFF-----KPLESFTTAAEL-----DYEKR	892
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	-----EKTFF-----KPLEGFTSAAKL-----DYEKR	894
tr A0A1Z1LY62 A0A1Z1LY62_9CAUD	-----NKTFF-----KPLTSFTTAAKI-----DYEKR	893
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	DNKPLCAEFFTRFLGVRPVFSN-----	1004
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	DNKVLSTSFERFMFGTKPIFY-----	1006
sp P0D005 DPOL_VAR67	DNKVLCSFFERFMFGSRPTFYEA-----	1005
sp P0D006 DPOL_VARV	DNKVLCSFFERFMFGSRPTFYEA-----	1005
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	DNKVLCSFFERFMFGSRPTFYEA-----	1006
sp Q57191 DPOL_VACCA	DNKVLCSFFERFMFGSKPTFYEA-----	1006
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	GSHTRAVISITSPNSGIMKFAKQQLTGLGKAVISGPNQTLCSHCKGREAEELYCKTVANV	1066
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	GSHTRAVISITSPNSGIMKFAKQQLTGLGKAVISGPNQTLCSHCKGREAEELYCKTVANV	1046
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	GSHTRSVISITSPNSGIMKFAKQQLTGLGKAVISGASQTLCSHCKGREAEELYCKTVANV	1046
sp Q9LRE6 DPD01_ORYSJ	GSHTRAVISITSPNSGIMKFAKQQLTGLGKAVISGPNQTLCSHCKGREAEELYCKTVANV	1048
sp Q9LVN7 DPD01_ARATH	GSHTRSISITTPNSGIMKFAKQQLTGLGKAVISGPNQTLCSHCKGREAEELYCKTVANV	1038
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	GDHMRISITTPNSGIMRFAKQQLSGLGKAVISGPNQTLCSHCKGREAEELYCKTVANV	1033
tr DOVEW7 DOVEW7_XENLA	GEHTRCKTVLTKVGGLLAFKRRNSCIGKATLNH--DGAVCNKYQRESELLQKEISQL	1048
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	GDHTRCKTVLTKVGGLLAFKRRNSCIGKRSVIDH--QGAVCKFCQPRESELYQKEVSHL	1040
sp P52431 DPD01_MOUSE	GDHTRCKTVLTKVGGLLAFKRRNSCIGKRSVIDH--QGAVCKFCQPRESELYQKEVSHL	1042
sp P28340 DPD01_HUMAN	GDHTRCKTVLTKVGGLLAFKRRNSCIGKRTVLSH--QGAVCKFCQPRESELYQKEVSHL	1044
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	GDHTRCKTVLTKVGGLLAFKRRNSCIGKRTVLSH--QGAVCKFCQPRESELYQKEVSHL	1044
tr M3VU04 M3VU04_FELCA	GDHTRCKTVLTKVGGLLAFKRRNSCIGKRTVLSH--QGAVCKFCQPRESELYQKEVSHL	1044
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	GDHTRCKTVLTKVGGLLAFKRRNSCIGKRTVLSH--QGAVCKFCQPRESELYQKEVSHL	1064
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	GDHTRCKTVLTKVGGLLAFKRRNSCIGKRTVLSH--QGAVCKFCQPRESELYQKEVSHL	1043

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	---GLF-----	783
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	---GLF-----	783
tr A0A5Y2S1M3 A0A5Y2S1M3_SALER	---GLF-----	783
tr A0A2B7LUW5 A0A2B7LUW5_9ESCH	---GLF-----	783
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	---GLF-----	783
tr A0A6N3R803 A0A6N3R803_SHIFL	---GLF-----	783
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	---GLF-----	783
tr A0A3P6LPK6 A0A3P6LPK6_SHIDY	---GLF-----	783
tr A0A0K0QSA0 A0A0K0QSA0_9CAUD	ASLNTLFGDDW---	901
tr A0A1W5POA4 A0A1W5POA4_9CAUD	ASLNTLFGDDW---	901
tr A0A7U3VGB5 A0A7U3VGB5_9CAUD	SSLMDMDFD---	901
tr A0A5Q2F6H2 A0A5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	SLLDMDFD---	902
tr A0A2K9VME2 A0A2K9VME2_9CAUD	ASLDLFLG---	947
tr A0A249XWD5 A0A249XWD5_9CAUD	ASLDLFLG---	898
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	ASLDLFLG---	898
tr A0A2U7NJH8 A0A2U7NJH8_9CAUD	GSLLDLFD---	900
tr A0A0B5A2H2 A0A0B5A2H2_9CAUD	ASLDDIFGW---	901
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	ASLFDMDFD---	903
tr A0A1Z1LY62 A0A1Z1LY62_9CAUD	ASLFDMDFD---	902
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	-----	1004
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	-----	1006
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	-----	1005
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VARV	-----	1005
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	-----	1006
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	-----	1006
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	SDLEMLFGKLTWCQDRCGSLHQDVLCTSRDPIFYRRRKAQKDMAEARVQLDRWDF---	1123
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	SDLEMLFGKLTWCQDRCGSLHQDVLCTSRDPIFYRRRKAQKDMAEARVQLDRWDF---	1103
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	SDLEMLFGRLWTCQDRCGSLHQDVLCTSRDPIFYRRRKAQKDMTEARLQDRWDF---	1103
sp Q9LRE6 DP0D1_ORYSJ	SELEMLFGRLWTCQDRCGSLHQDVLCTSRDPIFYRRRKAQKDMAEARVQLDRWDF---	1105
sp Q9LVN7 DP0D1_ARATH	AELEEVFGLRWTCQDRCGSLHQDVLCTSRDPIFYRRRKAQKDMAVARQQLDRWDF---	1095
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	SDLEELFGRLWTCQDRCGSLHQDVLCTSRDPIFYRRRKAQKDMATAKQLDRWDF---	1090
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	SALEEKFSRLWTCQDRCGSLHEEVLCTSRDPIFYMRKKVQKDLDDQEKLLTRFGPPA---	1107
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	NALEERFSRLWTCQDRCGSLHEDVICTSRDPIFYMRKKVRKDLEDQERLLQRFPGPPG---	1100
sp P52431 DP0D1_MOUSE	NALEERFSRLWTCQDRCGSLHEDVICTSRDPIFYMRKKVRKDLEDQERLLQRFPGPPG---	1102
sp P28340 DP0D1_HUMAN	NALEERFSRLWTCQDRCGSLHEDVICTSRDPIFYMRKKVRKDLEDQEQQLRRFGPPGP---	1104
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	NALEERFSRLWTCQDRCGSLHEDVICTSRDPIFYMRKKVRKDLEDQEQQLRRFGPPGP---	1104
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	NALEERFSRLWTCQDRCGSLHEDVICTSRDPIFYMRKKVRKDLEDQEQQLRRFGPPGP---	1104
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	NALEERFSRLWTCQDRCGSLHEDVICTSRDPIFYMRKKVRKDLEDQEQQLRRFGPPGP---	1124
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	SALEERFSRLWTCQDRCGSLHEDVICTSRDPIFYMRKKVRKDLEDQERLLRFGPPGP---	1103

//End of the 5 different replicative pol sequences

tr A8ALP2 A8ALP2_CITK8	---	783
tr D2TGG5 D2TGG5_CITRI	---	783
tr A0A5Y2S1M3 A0A5Y2S1M3_SALER	---	783
tr A0A2B7LUW5 A0A2B7LUW5_9ESCH	---	783
tr B7LVT1 B7LVT1_ESCF3	---	783
tr A0A6N3R803 A0A6N3R803_SHIFL	---	783
sp P21189 DPO2_ECOLI	---	783
tr A0A3P6LPK6 A0A3P6LPK6_SHIDY	---	783
tr A0A0K0QSA0 A0A0K0QSA0_9CAUD	---	901
tr A0A1W5POA4 A0A1W5POA4_9CAUD	---	901
tr A0A7U3VGB5 A0A7U3VGB5_9CAUD	---	901
tr A0A5Q2F6H2 A0A5Q2F6H2_9CAUD	---	902
tr A0A2K9VME2 A0A2K9VME2_9CAUD	---	947
tr A0A249XWD5 A0A249XWD5_9CAUD	---	898
sp P04415 DPOL_BPT4	---	898
tr A0A2U7NJH8 A0A2U7NJH8_9CAUD	---	900
tr A0A0B5A2H2 A0A0B5A2H2_9CAUD	---	901
sp Q38087 DPOL_BPR69	---	903
tr A0A1Z1LY62 A0A1Z1LY62_9CAUD	---	902
tr A0A1S7DLM5 A0A1S7DLM5_MCV2	---	1004
tr Q6TUX3 Q6TUX3_YMTV5	---	1006
sp P0DOO5 DPOL_VAR67	---	1005
sp P0DOO6 DPOL_VARV	---	1005
sp A0A7H0DN44 DPOL_MONPV	---	1006
sp O57191 DPOL_VACCA	---	1006
tr A0A287NEC0 A0A287NEC0_HORVV	---	1123
tr A0A3B6JHK9 A0A3B6JHK9_WHEAT	---	1103
tr A0A1D6QLT8 A0A1D6QLT8_MAIZE	---	1103
sp Q9LRE6 DP0D1_ORYSJ	---	1105
sp Q9LVN7 DP0D1_ARATH	---	1095
tr A0A078I2E2 A0A078I2E2_BRANA	---	1090
tr D0VEW7 D0VEW7_XENLA	--W	1108
tr G3V8M1 G3V8M1_RAT	EAW	1103
sp P52431 DP0D1_MOUSE	EAW	1105
sp P28340 DP0D1_HUMAN	EAW	1107
tr F7DXU3 F7DXU3_HORSE	EAW	1107
tr M3VUJ4 M3VUJ4_FELCA	EAW	1107
tr A0A5G2QET9 A0A5G2QET9_PIG	EAW	1127
tr E1BNZ6 E1BNZ6_BOVIN	EAW	1106

Bacterial DNA Pols	
A8ALP2, <i>Citrobacter koseri</i>	D2TGG5, <i>Citrobacter rodentium</i>
A0A5Y2S1M3, <i>Salmonella enterica</i>	A0A2B7LUW5, <i>Escherichia marmotae</i>
B7LVT1, <i>Escherichia fergusonii</i>	A0A6N3R803, <i>Shigella flexneri</i>
P21189 DPO2, <i>Escherichia coli</i> (strain K12)	A0A3P6LPK6, <i>Shigella dysenteriae</i>
Bacteriophage DNA Pols	
A0A0K0QSA0, <i>Citrobacter</i> phage	A0A1W5P0A4, <i>Cronobacter</i> phage
A0A7U3VGB5, <i>Acinetobacter</i> phage	A0A5Q2F6H2, <i>Klebsiella</i> phage
A0A2K9VME2, <i>Shigella</i> phage	A0A249XWD5, <i>Salmonella</i> phage
P04415, <i>Enterobacteria phage T4</i>	A0A2U7NJH8, <i>Pseudomonas</i> phage
A0A0B5A2H2, <i>Yersinia</i> phage	Q38087, <i>Escherichia</i> phage RB69
A0A1Z1LY62, <i>Serratia</i> phage	
Poxviral DNA Pols	
A0A1S7DLM5, <i>Molluscum contagiosum</i> virus	Q6TUX3, Yaba monkey tumor virus
P0DOO5, <i>Variola</i> virus (isolate Human/India/Ind3/1967)	P0DOO6, <i>Variola</i> virus
A0A7H0DN44, <i>Monkeypox</i> virus	O57191, <i>Vaccinia</i> virus (strain Ankara)
Plant δ DNA Pols	
A0A287NEC0, <i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	A0A3B6JHK9, Wheat
A0A1D6QLT8, <i>Zea mays</i>	Q9LRE6, <i>Oryza sativa</i> subsp. <i>japonica</i>
Q9LVN7, <i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	A0A078I2E2, <i>Brassica napus</i>
Animal δ DNA Pols	
D0VEW7, <i>Xenopus laevis</i>	G3V8M1, <i>Rattus norvegicus</i>
P52431, <i>Mus musculus</i>	P28340, <i>Homo sapiens</i>
F7DXU3, <i>Equus caballus</i>	M3VUJ4, <i>Felis catus</i>
A0A5G2QET9, <i>Sus scrofa</i>	E1BNZ6, <i>Bos taurus</i>

Figure 5 'Mix and match' MSA analysis of the replicative DNA pols from bacterial viruses, animal viruses (poxviruses), and from the replicative δ pols from plants and animals

4. Conclusions

The present study reveals both similarities and sharp differences between the replicative pols from poxviruses and other organisms, like bacteriophages, bacteria, yeasts, higher fungi, plants and animals. The pol and PR exonuclease domains are highly conserved in all these pols suggesting that these replicative DNA pols might have evolved possibly from a common ancestor gene and hence, could follow essentially the same mechanism of action. All the eukaryotic B-family pols possess the highly conserved -SLYPS- and -YGD TDS- motifs except the replicative ϵ pols. However, in the poxviral pols, the pentapeptide motif, -SLYPS- is slightly modified to -SLYPN-. However, the second motif is completely conserved in all. Another important difference between the poxviral pols and its host, i.e., human replicative pols is the presence of an HNH-type motif which is present only in the poxviral pols. Furthermore, the poxviral pols also differ in not possessing the regular ZBMs in their CTDs, which are invariably found in all three human replicative pols. A relatively thorough analyses of the poxvirus replication mechanism in mammalian cells could pave the way for the development of cost-effective antiviral drugs for this crucial enzyme to contain the spread of these deadly viruses in the future.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

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